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Abstract

CO₂ storage, transport and utilization costs could depend on national and regional regulations. For example, CO₂ storage monitoring costs, which depends on the requirements for monitoring, should be included into the storage costs. Most of the EU countries implemented EU CCS Directive by 2013. CO₂ use options were not included into EU CCS Directive (2009), but some CO₂ use issues appeared in Monitoring and Reporting Guidelines under the EU ETS Directive (Commission Decision 2007/589/EC and its amendment Commission Decision 2010/345/EU). CCS laws should be applied together with four guidelines to CCS Directive, EU Emission Trading System (EU ETS) and its Monitoring and Reporting Guidelines.

International and national regulations related to CCUS technology and their national implementations are compared for five countries (Italy, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania and Russia) involved in the planned CCUS scenarios of the CLEANKER project. Only Russia has not ratified yet Paris Climate Agreement. Latvia, Lithuania and Russia are not yet parties of the London Protocol. National GHG and CO₂ fossil emissions are compared with the base 1990 year and their climate and energy strategic targets are discussed. Russia is one of the largest emitters and Estonia has one of the highest CO₂ emissions per capita in the world. The climate strategic targets should be increased in all the studied countries to reach the Paris targets and CCUS technology should be included in the list of technological priorities together with renewables and other options in all the countries and in the BSR. CO₂ use options in the studied countries include CO₂ use for Enhanced Oil Recovery, Geothermal Energy Recovery and mineral carbonation using waste materials should be used in synergy with CO₂ storage and should compose business cases in both Italian and Baltic Scenarios. Additional CCUS regulations and political incentives, national, industrial and EU financial support are needed to start the first full CCUS projects in Italy, Baltic States and Russia. Educational and increasing public awareness activities supported by academic and research institutions and media support to explain benefits of climate change mitigation are needed for both scenarios and in the all countries.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABBREVIATIONS, TERMS AND UNITS.....	6
1. INTRODUCTION.....	8
2. NATIONAL CLIMATE TARGETS AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORKS	8
2.1 PARIS CLIMATE AGREEMENT.....	8
2.2 GHG EMISSIONS.....	9
2.3 CLIMATE STRATEGIES	10
3. MULTILATERAL ENVIRONMENTAL AGREEMENTS	12
3.1 LONDON CONVENTION AND LONDON PROTOCOL	12
3.2 OSPAR CONVENTION.....	15
4. EU CCS DIRECTIVE	18
4.1 IMPLEMENTATION OF EU CCS DIRECTIVE.....	19
4.2 AMENDMENT OF EXISTING EU DIRECTIVES	21
4.3 ASSESSING OF STORAGE CAPACITY AND APPLICATION FOR STORAGE PERMITS (ARTICLE 4(2))	22
4.4 MONITORING REQUIREMENTS	23
4.5 THIRD-PARTY ACCESS TO TRANSPORT NETWORK AND STORAGE SITE AND TRANSBOUNDARY ISSUES	26
5. PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION OF CCS	28
6. ASSESSMENT OF NATIONAL CCS REGULATIONS BY GCCSI.....	28
7. EUROPEAN UNION EMISSION TRADING SYSTEM (EU ETS)	29
7.4 MONITORING AND REPORTING GUIDELINES	31
8. INTEGRATION OF EU ETS AND EU CCS DIRECTIVE.....	32
9. REGULATIONS FOR CO₂ USE.....	32
9.1 CO ₂ USE FOR EOR.....	34
9.2 CO ₂ USE FOR GEOTHERMAL ENERGY RECOVERY (CO ₂ -GER).....	36
9.2.1 <i>Renewable Energy Directive</i>	37
9.2.2 <i>Geothermal Energy</i>	39
9.3 CO ₂ USE FOR CARBONATION OF HAZARDOUS WASTES	41
9.3.1 <i>Regulations for Hazardous Wastes</i>	41
1. The Waste Framework Directive.....	41
2. The Landfill Directive.....	42
3. The Basel Convention	42
9.4 CO ₂ MINERAL CARBONATION USING OIL SHALE ASH WASTE IN ESTONIA	43
9.4.1 <i>EU Waste Directive, Waste Act</i>	43
9.4.2 <i>National Waste Management Plan 2014-2020</i>	43
9.4.3 <i>Industrial Emissions Act</i>	44
9.4.4 <i>Reusing of oil shale ash</i>	44
9.5 WASTE ASH FROM ENERGY PRODUCTION IN RUSSIA	44
9.6 CO ₂ MINERAL CARBONATION USING CONCRETE DEMOLITION WASTE	45
9.6.1 <i>Italian case</i>	45
1. EU Waste Directive, Waste Act	45
2. Waste management plans (WMP) and Strategies.....	45
3. Definitions of waste treatment operations	46

9.6.2	<i>Estonian Case</i>	46
1.	<i>EU Waste Directive, Waste Act</i>	46
2.	<i>National Waste Management Plan 2014-2020</i>	46
3.	<i>The Environmental Charges Act</i>	46
10.	SUMMARY FOR COUNTRIES	47
10.1	ITALY	47
10.2	ESTONIA	50
10.3	LATVIA	53
10.4	LITHUANIA	56
10.5	RUSSIA	59
11.	GAPS IN AVAILABLE REGULATIONS AND CLIMATE STRATEGIES	61
11.1	INTERNATIONAL REGULATIONS	61
11.2	CCS DIRECTIVE AND STRATEGIC PLANNING	62
11.3	CO ₂ USE	63
11.3.1	<i>CO₂ use for enhanced recovery of resources</i>	63
11.3.2	<i>CO₂ mineral carbonation using wastes</i>	64
12.	RECOMMENDATIONS FOR REGULATIONS UPDATES, POLITICAL INCENTIVES AND OTHER NEEDED ACTIONS	64
12.1	ITALIAN SCENARIO	64
12.2	BALTIC SCENARIO	65
13.	CONCLUSIONS	66
14.	REFERENCES	67

ABBREVIATIONS, TERMS AND UNITS

Abbreviations

Bln – Billion
BSR – Baltic Sea Region
CCS – CO₂ capture and storage
CCS – EOR - enhanced oil recovery with permanent CO₂ geological storage
CGS – CO₂ geological storage
CO₂ - carbon dioxide
CO₂ - EGS – Enhanced geothermal systems using CO₂
CO₂ - EOR – Enhanced Oil Recovery using CO₂
CO₂ - GER – Enhanced Geothermal Energy Recovery using CO₂
CAT – Climate Action Tracker
CCUS – CO₂ capture, utilization and storage
CDW – Concrete Demolition Waste
COP21 – Conference of the Parties 21
CPG – CO₂ plume geothermal
EDGAR – Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research
EGS – Enhanced geothermal system
ENI – Italian multinational oil and gas company headquartered in Rome
EOR – Enhanced Oil Recovery
EHR – Enhanced Hydrocarbon Recovery
EU – European Union
EU28 – European Union 28 Member States
EU ETS - EU Emissions Trading System
GCCSI – Global Carbon Capture and Storage Institute
GER – Geothermal Energy Recovery
GHG – greenhouse gas
GHGE – greenhouse gas emissions
HELCOM - Helsinki Convention 1992
IMO – The International Maritime Organization
INDC – Intended Nationally Determined Contribution
KGDP – Klaipeda Geothermal Demonstration Plant
KNC – AS Kunda Nordic Tsement
LC – London Convention
LP – London Protocol
LULUCF – Land use, land-use change, and forestry. Defined by the UNFCCC Secretariat as a "greenhouse gas inventory sector that covers emissions and removals of greenhouse gases resulting from direct human-induced land use such as settlements and commercial uses, land-use change, and forestry activities".
MARPOL – International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships
MgO – Magnesium oxide
Mln – Million
MRG - Monitoring and Reporting Guidelines
NDC –Nationally Determined Contribution
N₂O – Nitrous Oxide

PA – Paris Agreement
PFC – Perfluorocarbon
RE – Renewable Energy
RES – Renewable Energy Sources
SDAP – Spray-Dried Absorption Product
WFD – Waste Framework Directive
WMP – Waste Management Plan
WP7 – Work Package 7
UGS – Underground gas storage
UNCLOS – United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
UNFCCC – United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

Terms

Baltic Region – Baltic States (Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania)
Baltic Sea Region – Denmark, Estonia, Latvia, Finland, Germany, Lithuania, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Norway and Belarus
Baltic Sea Area – For the purposes of the HELCOM Convention the "Baltic Sea Area" shall be the Baltic Sea and the entrance to the Baltic Sea bounded by the parallel of the Skaw in the Skagerrak at 57° 44.43'N.
London Protocol – Protocol to the Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matter
OSPAR Convention – Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic

Units

CO₂/cap/yr – CO₂ emissions per capita per year
Gt – gigatonne
GtCO₂e – gigatonne of CO₂ emissions
m – metre
km – kilometre
Kt – kilo tonnes
Ktoe – kilotonnes oil equivalent
Mtoe – million tonnes oil equivalent
Mt – million tonnes
Mt CO₂ eq – million tonnes in CO₂ equivalent
Mt/yr – million tonnes per year
MW – megawatts
GW – gigawatts
TW – terawatts
t – tonnes
t/yr – tonnes per year
T, °C – temperature by Celsius
TJ – Terajoule

1. INTRODUCTION

The main objective of the WP7 of the CLEANKER project is to explore local and regional transport, utilization and storage needs, options and solutions in the vicinity of the demo system Vernasca Cement Plant in Italy (Lombardy Region), the Kunda Nordic Cement plant (KNC) in Estonia and Slantsev Cement Plant "Cesla" OJSC in Russia located in 16 km from Estonia-Russian border and 25-30 km from the largest Estonian power plants (Eesti, Balti and Auvere power plants).

Uncertainty and gaps in CCUS regulations is reported as one of the main barriers for wide implementation of this technology (Shogenova et al, 2014, Chiang, 2017). Some countries have implemented market related policies or schemes to CCUS projects, such as carbon emission trading, carbon tax and contract electricity pricing, etc. Market related policies for CCUS should be developed considering available in the world experience, local conditions, should improve the existing policies, make policy innovations, so that the development of CCUS can be facilitated in the early R&D stage and can be fully supported in the later CCUS commercial operation stage (GCCSI & GIEC, 2013).

In this report national strategic energy and climate targets, implemented international regulations, national policies, implemented national regulations of four EU countries (Italy, Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania) and Russia are discussed and compared. Gaps are revealed and new regulatory incentives which will enable implementation of CCUS scenarios are recommended.

2. NATIONAL CLIMATE TARGETS AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORKS

2.1 Paris Climate Agreement

A global climate agreement was reached in December 2015 in Paris at the 21st Conference of the Parties (COP21) of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC, 2018).

Table 2.1: Ratification of Paris Climate Agreement (UNFCCC, 2018)

Country	Signature	Ratification
Italy	22 Apr 2016	11 Nov 2016
Estonia	22 Apr 2016	4 Nov 2016
Latvia	22 Apr 2016	16 Mar 2017
Lithuania	22 Apr 2016	2 Feb 2017
Russia	22 Apr 2016	Pending

In Paris, the countries agreed to hold the increase in the global average temperature to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels and to pursue efforts to limit the temperature increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels by 2100. This will significantly reduce the risks and impacts of climate change. The agreement entered into force on 4 November 2016, and 178 Parties have already ratified of 197 Parties to the Convention, including Italy, Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania. In June 2018 Russia has not yet ratified this agreement (Table 2.1).

2.2 GHG emissions

The Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research EDGAR (EC JRC, 2018) estimates CO₂ and other greenhouse gases for all world countries and aims to contribute to an enhanced transparency. EDGAR dataset (2016) revealed that Global CO₂ emissions are for the third year in a row plateauing with no further increase to a total of 35.8 Gt CO₂ in 2016. The global CO₂ per capita emissions were 4.8 t/yr. The EU28 emissions mainly decreased over the past two decades reaching reduction levels in 2016 of 20.8% compared to 1990 and 17.9% compared to 2005. This yields since 2015 a constant EU share to the global total of 9.6%. In 2016 the EU28 emitted 3.4 Gt CO₂, which corresponds to 6.75 t CO₂ emissions per capita (Janssens-Maenhout et al, 2017, EC JRC, 2018).

However, in 2016 in the studied EU countries both total CO₂ emissions and CO₂ emissions per capita have increased compared to 2015 (Table 2.2). In 2016 CO₂ emissions per capita were lower than world and EU averages only in Latvia and Lithuania, while in Italy CO₂/cap/yr emissions were higher than in the world and only 0.72 t lower than EU28 average. CO₂ emissions per capita were higher than in the world and EU28 average in Russia and in Estonia (Table 2.2). Estonian CO₂ emissions per capita were 3.5 times higher than in the world and 2.5 times higher than EU28 average. Estonian emissions per capita were at the second place in Europe (after Luxemburg) and at 11-12th place in the world (EC JRC, 2018).

Table 2.2: Fossil CO₂ Emissions (Janssens-Maenhout et al, 2017, EC JRC, 2018)

Country	CO ₂ total emissions (Mt/yr)			CO ₂ per capita emissions (t CO ₂ /cap/yr)		
	1990	2015	2016	1990	2015	2016
Italy	423.3	355.14	358.14	7.41	5.97	6.03
Estonia	36.97	22.18	22.40	23.55	16.8	17.1
Latvia	20.32	7.89	8.16	7.64	3.96	4.14
Lithuania	35.1	13.33	13.69	9.49	4.55	4.7
Russia	2379.4	1698	1662	16.08	11.79	11.54

National reports submitted by countries in 2018 to UNFCCC according to Kyoto obligations reported that the total GHG emissions excluding forests (LULUCF) increased in 2016 compared by 2015 in Estonia and Russia (UNFCCC 2018). Considering relatively large forest areas in all the studied countries the reported total GHG emission including LULUCF are significantly lower in all countries (Table 2.3).

Table 2.3: Total greenhouse gas emissions and removals in CO₂ equivalent (Mt CO₂ eq) reported by countries to UNFCCC (UNFCCC 2018)

Country	Total GHG emissions in CO ₂ equivalent (Mt CO ₂ eq) (excluding LULUCF)			Total GHG emissions in CO ₂ equivalent (Mt CO ₂ eq) (including LULUCF)		
	1990	2015	2016	1990	2015	2016
Italy	518.363	432.878	427.862	515.321	397.552	397.935
Estonia	40.4	18.05	19.63	38.85	15.8	16.9
Latvia	26.47	12.04	11.31	15.77	11.33	10.38
Lithuania	48.1	20.17	20.054	42.97	14.03	11.57
Russia	3893.1	2629.9	2643.8	3734.3	2026.8	2009.4

2.3 Climate strategies

The EU 2030 climate and energy framework sets three key targets for the year 2030 compared to 1990 levels: (1) at least 40% cuts in greenhouse gas emissions, at least 27% share for renewable energy and at least 27% improvement in energy efficiency. The framework was adopted by EU leaders in October 2014. It builds on the 2020 climate and energy package (20-20-20% reductions of (1)-(3) by 2020). The longer term perspective set out in the Roadmap for moving to a competitive low carbon economy in 2050, the Energy Roadmap 2050 and the Transport White Paper. EU low-carbon economy roadmap suggests that by 2050, the EU should cut greenhouse gas emissions to 80% below 1990 levels. Milestones to achieve this are 40% emissions cuts by 2030 and 60% by 2040 (Table 2.4, EC, 2018).

The EU's present 2030 target of reducing emissions by "at least 40%" below 1990 levels represents only a slight increase in the rate of climate action compared to the preceding quarter-century at exactly the time when there needs to be a significant acceleration in order to achieve the necessary decarbonisation by mid-century. This target was rated by Climate Action Tracker as "Insufficient" (CAT, 2018).

EU 2050 goal of decreasing total GHG emissions by 80–95% below 1990 levels is also not consistent with the Paris Agreement long term warming goal. The new EU long-term greenhouse gas emissions strategy, that the Commission was called to prepare by the

Member States by the first quarter of 2019, offers an opportunity to increase the level of ambition to reflect the 1.5°C temperature limit (CAT, 2018).

By 2050, Estonia is aiming to decrease greenhouse gas emissions (GHGE) by nearly 80% compared to the level of 1990. To reach these targets, by 2030 about 70% of GHGE and by 2040 about 72% of GHGE should be reduced (Table 2.4). If the policies are implemented, then by 2050, GHGE will have decreased the most in the energy sector and industry (by 67%) (Keskkonnaministeerium, 2017).

Italian National Energy Strategy 2017 aims to

- reduce final energy consumption by a total of 10 Mtoe by 2030;
- reach a 28% share of renewables in total energy consumption by 2030, and a 55% share of renewables in electricity consumption by 2030;
- strengthen supply security; to narrow the energy price gap;
- furthering sustainable public mobility and eco-friendly fuels and phasing out the use of coal in electricity generation by 2025 (Italy's National Energy Strategy, 2017).

Table 2.4: National Absolute Emission Reduction Targets

Country	Kyoto target 2013-2020 (%)	Compared to 1990 (%)			The latest policy documents
		2030	2040	2050	
Italy	20	40	60	80	EU Decision 529/2013
Estonia	20	70	72	80	Keskkonnaministeerium, 2017
Latvia	20	40	60	80	EU Decision 529/2013
Lithuania	20	40	60	80	Ministry of Environment Lithuania, 2012.
Russia	-	25-30	NA	NA	Decree of the President of the Russian Federation (RF) of 30.09. 2013. Act of the Government of the RF of 2.04. 2014 No. 504-p. Climate Doctrine and the Energy Strategy of the RF.

On the 31 March 2015, the Russian Federation submitted its 2030 Intended Nationally Determined Contribution (INDC), proposing to reduce emissions 25% to 30% below 1990 levels by 2030 (UNFCCC 2015). The Russian government officially signed the Paris Agreement (PA) on April 22, 2016. The ratification of the agreement and thus the submission of the definitive Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) are still pending and Russia has presented a national strategy that may delay ratification until at least 2019.

Russia stated that “Limiting anthropogenic greenhouse gases in Russia to 70-75% of 1990 levels by the year 2030 might be a long-term indicator, subject to the maximum possible account of absorbing capacity of forests.” (UNFCCC, 2015).

According to latest estimates of Climate Action Tracker (CAT, 2017), Russia’s currently implemented policies will lead to emissions of 2.6 GtCO_{2e} in 2020 and 2.7GtCO_{2e} in 2030 (both excluding LULUCF), which is 4% and 11% above 2015 emissions levels, respectively. This represents a decrease in emissions from 1990 levels of 28% in 2020 and 23% in 2030, all below the INDC targets, which allow emissions to grow 8–27% above 2015 levels by 2020 and 18–25% by 2030.

A first step towards contributing to the Paris Agreement’s goals would be to speed up the national process for ratification of the Agreement and present a 2030 target which sets out actual emissions reductions beyond the current policy scenario. This would not only be more credible from an international perspective but would also help to align national policy developments with the long-term emission reductions needed to avoid dangerous levels of climate change (CAT, 2018).

3. MULTILATERAL ENVIRONMENTAL AGREEMENTS

At the international level, major regulations that affect CCS are international conventions dealing with transboundary shipments of CO₂. Such agreements are the Protocol to the Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matter (London Protocol) and OSPAR Convention. All the Baltic Sea Region countries, including Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania and Russia, are contracting parties of the Helsinki Convention 1992 (HELCOM) aiming on the protection of the Baltic marine environment, including regulation of dumping, pollution as well as exploration and exploitation activities of the seabed and its subsoil in the Baltic Sea.

One of the issues raised by the SET-plan Action 9, and outlined within the Implementation Plan is the current status of the London Protocol. This prohibits the export of CO₂ from a contracting party to other countries for injection into subseabed geological formations. The protocol was amended in 2009 to enable cross-border CCS projects, but the amendment must be ratified by two-thirds of contracting parties to enter into force. Given the required number of ratifications and difficulties associated with the ratification process, it appears unlikely that two-thirds of contracting parties will be in a position to ratify the amendment in the near term. Raising awareness among relevant government ministries of the importance to global CCS deployment of ratifying the London Protocol amendment should be a priority (EU, 2017).

3.1 London Convention and London Protocol

London Convention. The Inter-Governmental Conference entitled “The Convention on the Dumping of Wastes at Sea”, which occurred in London in November 1972 at the invitation

of the United Kingdom, agreed on a set of guidelines, generally known as the London Convention (LC). The London Convention, one of the first international conventions for the protection of the marine environment from human activities, came into force on 30 August 1975. Since 1977, it has been administered by IMO (The International Maritime Organization). Currently, 87 States are Party to the London Convention 1972 (Figure 3.1).

The London Convention contributes to the international control and prevention of marine pollution by prohibiting the dumping of certain hazardous materials. In addition, a special permit is required prior to dumping of a number of other identified materials and a general permit for other wastes or matter. "Dumping" has been defined as the deliberate disposal at sea of wastes or other matter from vessels, aircraft, platforms or other man-made structures, as well as the deliberate disposal of these vessels or platforms themselves. Annexes list wastes which cannot be dumped and others for which a special dumping permit is required. Amendments adopted in 1993 (which entered into force in 1994) banned the dumping into the sea of low-level radioactive wastes. In addition, the amendments phased out the dumping of industrial wastes by 31 December 1995 and banned the incineration at sea of industrial wastes.

London Protocol. In 1996, Parties adopted a Protocol to the Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matter, 1972 (known as the London Protocol (LP)) which entered into force in 2006. The London Protocol is a separate treaty from the Convention and may be ratified by States without being a party to the Convention. The London Protocol is the more modern and comprehensive of the two global treaties relating to the prevention of marine pollution from dumping at sea. The Protocol provides the precautionary framework needed for parties to effectively prevent pollution of the sea caused by dumping of waste and other matter, incineration, and new activities such as marine geoengineering or carbon capture and storage. The London Protocol is one of the key pillars of marine environmental protection in an important international regime that includes MARPOL, UNCLOS and Regional Seas Agreements.

In May 2018 there were 50 Parties to the London Protocol 1996, 87 parties to the London Convention 1972 and 99 parties in total (LC and LP) (Figure 3.1, IMO, 2017 a). Among studied countries Russia is a party to the London Convention 1972, but have not ratified the London Protocol 1996. Latvia and Lithuania are not parties to either the London Convention or the London Protocol, Italy has ratified both the LC and LP, and Estonia has ratified LP in 2013 (IMO, 2017b). The Protocol, which is meant to eventually replace the 1972 Convention, represents a major change of approach to the question of how to regulate the use of the sea as a depository for waste materials. Rather than stating which materials may not be dumped, it prohibits all dumping, except for possibly acceptable wastes on the so-called "reverse list", contained in an annex to the Protocol.

The London Protocol stresses the "precautionary approach", which requires that "appropriate preventative measures are taken when there is reason to believe that wastes or

other matter introduced into the marine environment are likely to cause harm even when there is no conclusive evidence to prove a causal relation between inputs and their effects". It also states that "the polluter should, in principle, bear the cost of pollution" and emphasizes that Contracting Parties should ensure that the Protocol should not simply result in pollution being transferred from one part of the environment to another.

The Contracting Parties to the London Convention and Protocol have recently taken steps to mitigate the impacts of increasing concentrations of CO₂ in the atmosphere (and consequently in the marine environment) and to ensure that new technologies that aim to engineer the climate, and have the potential to cause harm to the marine environment, are effectively controlled and regulated.

The instruments have, so far, been the most advanced international regulatory instruments addressing carbon capture and sequestration in sub-sea geological formations and marine climate engineering such as ocean fertilization.

Figure 3.1: Parties of London Convention 1972 and London Protocol 1996 (IMO, 2017 a).

The 1996 Protocol restricts all dumping except for a permitted list (which still require permits). In order to enable sub-seabed storage the parties to the protocol adopted an amendment in 2006 where CO₂ sequestration in sub-seabed geological formations was added to the Protocol Annex 1 (LP.1(1)). This amendment entered into the force on 10 February 2007. Also in 2007 "Specific Guidelines for Assessment of Carbon Dioxide

Streams for disposal into Sub-seabed geological Formations” were adopted by the Protocol Parties.

Article 4 states that Contracting Parties "shall prohibit the dumping of any wastes or other matter with the exception of those listed in Annex 1:

CO₂ streams from CO₂ capture processes are in the list of the permitted substances.

The amendments state that:

- carbon dioxide streams may only be considered for dumping, if:
- disposal is into a sub-seabed geological formation;
- they consist overwhelmingly of carbon dioxide (they may contain incidental associated substances derived from the source material and the capture and sequestration processes used);
- No wastes or other matter are added for the purpose of disposing of them.

Amendment to Article 6 of the LP was adopted in 2009. Article 6 prohibits “export of wastes or other matter to other countries for dumping or incineration at sea.” 2009 amendments to Article 6 (LP.3(4)) enabling - exclusively - the export of carbon dioxide streams for the purpose of sequestration in trans-boundary sub-seabed geological formations, is not yet in force. By May 2018 it is accepted only by five countries (Finland, Iran, The Netherlands, Norway and UK), while amendment to the LP requires acceptance by two-third of the Parties to enter into force (IMO, 2017b). All countries studied in these report, among which only Italy and Estonia are London Protocol parties, have not yet ratified amendment to the article 6 of the LP (Table 3.1).

Large point sources of CO₂ emissions, including power plants and cement works, could capture and store CO₂ in sub-seabed geological formations for permanent isolation. Although several demonstration and R&D projects are taking place, no permits have yet been issued under the London Protocol. Some options for transboundary storage of CO₂ regulated by Article 6 of the LP and CCS Directive are described in (Rydberg and Langlet 2014).

3.2 OSPAR Convention

Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (OSPAR Convention, 1992) is the mechanism by which fifteen Governments of the western coasts and catchments of Europe, together with the European Community, cooperate to protect the marine environment of the North-East Atlantic (Figure 3.2, Figure 3.3). It started in 1972 with the Oslo Convention against dumping. It was broadened to cover land-based sources and the offshore industry by the Paris Convention of 1974. These two conventions were unified, up-dated and extended by the 1992 OSPAR Convention. The new annex on biodiversity and ecosystems was adopted in 1998 to cover non-polluting human activities that can adversely affect the sea (OSPAR COMMISSION, 2018). The OSPAR Convention text as amended in 1998 was updated in 2002 and then in 2005 and 2006. Amendments to Annexes II and II adopted at OSPAR 2007.

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Under the Rules of Procedure the OSPAR Commission consists of representatives of each of its 16 Contracting Parties (Table 3.1). The Contracting Parties are Belgium, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Iceland, Ireland, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom, together with the European Union. Finland is not on the western coasts of Europe, but some of its rivers flow to the Barents Sea and historically it was involved in the efforts to control the dumping of hazardous waste in the Atlantic and the North Sea. Luxembourg and Switzerland are Contracting Parties due to their location within the catchments of the River Rhine.

Figure 3.2: Parties of OSPAR Convention
 ■ Signatory states
 ■ European Union

Figure 3.3: OSPAR maritime area – the Arctic (I), the Greater North Sea (II), the Celtic Seas, the Bay of Biscay/Golfe de Gascogne (III) and Iberian waters (IV), and the Wider Atlantic (V) www.ospar.org

Annex II on the prevention and elimination of pollution by dumping or incineration includes article 1, stating that this Annex shall not apply to any deliberate disposal in the maritime area of: (a) wastes or other matter from offshore installations; (b) offshore installations and offshore pipelines; article 2 (Incineration is prohibited) and article 3:

- The dumping of all wastes or other matter is prohibited, except for those wastes or other matter listed in paragraphs 2 and 3 of this Article.

The list referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article includes the following:

(f) carbon dioxide streams from carbon dioxide capture processes for storage, provided:

- disposal is into a sub-soil geological formation;
- the streams consist overwhelmingly of carbon dioxide. They may contain incidental associated substances derived from the source material and the capture, transport and storage processes used;
- no wastes or other matter are added for the purpose of disposing of those wastes or other matter;

- they are intended to be retained in these formations permanently and will not lead to significant adverse consequences for the marine environment, human health and other legitimate uses of the maritime area.

3.3 Helsinki Convention 1992 (HELCOM)

The 1992 Helsinki Convention, Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area, entered into force on 17 January 2000, after the ratification instruments were deposited by the European Economic Community, Germany, Latvia and Sweden in 1994, by Estonia and Finland in 1995, by Denmark in 1996, by Lithuania in 1997, and by Poland and Russia in November 1999 (HELCOM, 2018)

The Convention covers the whole of the Baltic Sea area, including inland waters as well as the water of the sea itself and the sea-bed. Measures are also taken in the whole catchment area of the Baltic Sea to reduce land-based pollution. The Convention is amended when deemed necessary, thus following, e.g., the developments in international environmental and maritime laws. The latest amendment entered into force on 15 November 2008 (HELCOM, 2018).

HELCOM Convention is applied to the Baltic Sea Area. For the purposes of this Convention the "Baltic Sea Area" shall be the Baltic Sea and the entrance to the Baltic Sea bounded by the parallel of the Skaw in the Skagerrak at 57° 44.43'N. The Contracting Parties shall individually or jointly take all appropriate legislative, administrative or other relevant measures to prevent and eliminate pollution in order to promote the ecological restoration of the Baltic Sea Area and the preservation of its ecological balance (HELCOM, 2014).

This Convention shall apply to the protection of the marine environment of the Baltic Sea Area which comprises the water-body and the seabed including their living resources and other forms of marine life. Without prejudice to its sovereignty each Contracting Party shall implement the provisions of this Convention within its territorial sea and its internal waters through its national authorities.

Whenever an environmental impact assessment of a proposed activity that is likely to cause a significant adverse impact on the marine environment of the Baltic Sea Area is required by international law or supra-national regulations applicable to the Contracting Party of origin, that Contracting Party shall notify the Commission and any Contracting Party which may be affected by a transboundary impact on the Baltic Sea Area.

Where two or more Contracting Parties share transboundary waters within the catchment area of the Baltic Sea, these Parties shall cooperate to ensure that potential impacts on the marine environment of the Baltic Sea Area are fully investigated within the environmental impact assessment referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article. The Contracting Parties concerned shall jointly take appropriate measures in order to prevent and eliminate pollution including cumulative deleterious effects.

The Contracting Parties shall prohibit dumping in the Baltic Sea Area. Dumping of dredged material shall be subject to a prior special permit issued by the appropriate national

authority. Each Contracting Party shall take all measures in order to prevent pollution of the marine environment of the Baltic Sea Area resulting from exploration or exploitation of its part of the seabed and the subsoil thereof or from any associated activities thereon as well as to ensure that adequate preparedness is maintained for immediate response actions against pollution incidents caused by such activities.

The Contracting Parties shall ensure that information is made available to the public on the condition of the Baltic Sea and the waters in its catchment area, measures taken or planned to be taken to prevent and eliminate pollution and the effectiveness of those measures.

For this purpose, the Contracting Parties shall ensure that the following information is made available to the public: a) permits issued and the conditions required to be met; b) results of water and effluent sampling carried out for the purposes of monitoring and assessment, as well as results of checking compliance with water-quality objectives or permit conditions; and c) water-quality objectives.

Each Contracting Party shall ensure that this information shall be available to the public at all reasonable times and shall provide members of the public with reasonable facilities for obtaining, on payment of reasonable charges, copies of entries in its registers.

Table 3.1: Participation of countries in international agreements regulating offshore storage

International agreements (offshore storage)						
Country	London Convention 1972	London Protocol 1996, LP	Amendments to LP		HELCO M 1992	OSPAR 1992
			2006 LP.1 (1)	2009 article 6 (LP.3 (4))		
Italy	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	NA	EU sign
Estonia		Yes	Yes	No	Yes	EU sign
Latvia	No	No	No	No	Yes	EU sign
Lithuania	No	No	No	No	Yes	EU sign
Russia	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No

4. EU CCS DIRECTIVE

Directive 2009/31/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the geological storage of carbon dioxide (so-called Carbon Capture and Storage Directive – hereinafter ‘CCS Directive’) establishes a legal framework for the environmentally safe geological

storage of CO₂. The CCS Directive aims to ensure that there is no significant risk of leakage of CO₂ or damage to health or the environment, and to prevent any adverse effects on the security of the transport network or storage sites (EC, 2009a).

4.1 Implementation of EU CCS Directive

Public authorities of the studied EU countries responsible for implementation of the EU CCS Directive (Table 4.1) reported to the EC about results from the CCS Directive transposition in 2013 and 2016.

Italy. In order to implement Directive 2009/31/EC, Italy passed a new legislation to regulate the geological storage of carbon. Legislative Decree No 162 of 14 September 2011 entered into force on 5 October 2011 (Decreto Legislativo n. 162, 2011).

Estonia. Various scientific studies have indicated that the territory, exclusive economic zone and continental shelf of Estonia are unsuitable for CO₂ storage within the meaning of UNCLOS and Directive 2009/31/EU. Therefore, the Earth's Crust Act and the draft Act amending the Water Act, prohibit the geological storage of CO₂ in both the earth's crust or in sea areas. The exploration permits stipulated in Article 5 of the Directive 2009/31/EC are not used in Estonia. Although there are no specific CO₂ storage capacity studies ordered by the legal authority, published studies of Estonian researchers indicate that CO₂ storage is very unfavourable for onshore storage (Shogenova et al, 2009a, b, 2011).

Latvia. Amendments have been made to national legislation in Latvia for the purpose of transposing the Directive. A framework has been established for obtaining permits for capture installations to carry out polluting activities, requirements have been set to regulate CO₂ transportation and a purity criterion has been established. The Saeima (Latvian Parliament) has adopted legislative amendments prohibiting the storage of CO₂ within Latvia's borders, its exclusive economic zone, and on its continental shelf. The duration of the ban is dependent on information to be provided by the Ministry of Environmental Protection and Regional Development to the Parliament. The Latvian Parliament will then use this information to determine whether to lift or maintain the ban.

The main reasons for taking the decision to prohibit storage in Latvia include:

- lack of experience in using CCS technology on an industrial scale and dealing with its environmental impact
- opposition from experts in the environmental authorities and from environmental organisations
- the absence of demand for CCS from Latvia's energy and industrial operators, as natural gas is used as a fuel almost exclusively, and the capacity of combustion plants is small compared to the rest of the EU
- Latvia's subterranean structures are intended to be used primarily for natural gas storage and for obtaining geothermal energy.

Lithuania. Two new legal acts were adopted in Lithuania to regulate the licensing system related to the implementation of the Directive:

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- Law of the Republic of Lithuania on Geological Storage of Carbon Dioxide No 91-4325, date of entry into force – 2011-07-19, thereafter referred to as “the Law” (Official Gazette, 2011a).
- Resolution No 1166 of the Government of the Republic of Lithuania of 5 October 2011 on the approval of the description of the procedure for exploration of carbon dioxide geological complexes, use and closure of carbon dioxide storage sites (No 5833-123), date of entry into force – 2011-10-14, thereafter referred to as “the Description”(Official Gazette, 2011b). Also in 28 legal acts Lithuania has transposed into national law the specific provisions of the CCS Directive.

Among the Baltic States only Lithuania allowed CO₂ geological storage both onshore and offshore. CO₂ storage is prohibited except for research and development in Estonia and Latvia. The EU CCS Directive is applied only to CO₂ storage amounts of more than 100000 tonnes. Therefore CO₂ injection is permitted for research and pilot projects in all the EU countries (Table 2.1). Italia permitted CO₂ storage except for the seismic areas (EC, 2014). The progress in EU CCS Directive implementation in 2013-2016 is presented in 2017 by the EC (EC, 2017a).

Table 4.1: Public authorities of the studied countries responsible for implementation of the EU CCS Directive

Country	Competent Authority	Roles
Italy	The Ministry of the Environment	Coordination among the different competent authorities with regards to the permitting procedure for carbon storage is the key point of the 2011 Decree. The concerted actions among the different ministries is regulated by clear instructions regarding communication arrangements, timeframes and deadlines for the various procedural phases, the binding nature of the opinions requested, and the use of collegiality for implementing and carrying out some of the procedural phases.
	Ministry of Economic Development (responsible for post-closer storage site monitoring)	
Estonia	Ministry of the Environment	Only competent authority, except in the case of construction of a transboundary transport pipeline, which requires a permit from the Government.
Latvia	Ministry of Environmental Protection and Regional Development	Coordinates the implementation of the CCS Directive and cooperates with the Ministry of Justice in matters concerning the

		determination of jurisdiction and transboundary transport.
	State Office of Environmental Monitoring	Ensures that the capture and storage for plants greater than 300 MW are evaluated.
	State Environmental Service	Incorporates “capture readiness” requirements for combustion plants in their permits and is responsible for setting the requirements for CO ₂ stream composition.
	A Court of General Jurisdiction	Responsible for dispute settlement.
Lithuania	Geological Survey of Lithuania	Competent authority which performs most of the tasks referred to in the Directive.
	Lithuanian Government	Determines the cases under which the decision to transfer responsibility shall be agreed with the Commission.
	Ministry of Environment	Makes decisions on the transfer of responsibility.

4.2 Amendment of existing EU Directives

The CCS Directive has amended six existing EU Directives in order to protect the environment and human health from the risks connected to geological storage of CO₂. All EU Member States, communicated the EC for their transposing measures, made amendments in four of their existing instruments regulated by the

- (1) EIA (Environmental Impact Assessment) Directive,
- (2) Waste Framework Directive,
- (3) Industrial Emission Directive and
- (4) Large Combustion Plant Directive.

Member States which allow CO₂ storage in their countries also amended laws regulated by

- (5) Water Framework Directive and
- (6) Environmental Liability Directive (Articles 31-35 and 37; EC, 2009a and EC, 2014).

As a result:

- capture and transport of CO₂ stream is covered by national instruments regulated by (1) and (3),
- CO₂ captured and transported for the purpose of geological storage is excluded from the national waste regulations (2),
- and operators of combustion plants with capacity of 300 MW or more should assess conditions and demonstrate that the plant is built “capture-ready” (4) in all the Member States.

Table 4.2: National CCS laws

Country	CO ₂ storage permitted for			Exploration permit always required
	Industrial Scale		Research	
	On-shore	Off-shore		
Italy	Except for seismic areas	Except for seismic areas	Yes	Yes
Estonia	No	No	Yes	NA
Latvia	No	No	Yes	Yes
Lithuania	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

CO₂ is allowed for injection into saline reservoirs according to instruments regulated by (5) and operation of CO₂ storage sites is allowed according to amendments made in instruments regulated by (6) in countries permitting CO₂ storage (EC, 2014, Shogenova et. al., 2014).

4.3 Assessing of storage capacity and application for storage permits (Article 4(2))

Italy is completing a Strategic Environmental Assessment that will allow assessing the available storage capacity. Among studied countries an application for a storage permit was under evaluation only in Italy (EC, 2017a).

When examining and assessing the storage capacity available on the national territory as well as when granting exploration and temporary storage permits, the competent authorities in Italy must refer to Annex 1 of the Decree, which contains all the technical parameters specified in Annex 1 of the Directive (Decreto Legislativo n. 162, 2011).

Article 8(1) of the Decree stipulates that new surveys and exploration is allowed for the selection of storage sites by means of a special permit, if the information available (from the database referred to in Article 6) is not sufficient.

In the Annex to EC Report, 2017 (EC, 2017a) it is stated that the majority of current assessments done in the Member States are static and do not include aspects such as flow calculations, migration pathways and dissolution effects. Studying these parameters would be necessary for choosing the most appropriate monitoring techniques and for the optimisation of potential CO₂ storage projects. Cost models would also improve the usefulness of CO₂ storage assessments.

Two pilot injections have been already made in Lithuania in 2013, investigating potential of CO₂ to be used for EOR (Haselton, 2013). In addition to the storage capacity in Lithuania, reported in EU GeoCapacity project (Vangkilde-Pedersen et.al., 2009), about 100 Mt in saline aquifers of Gargždai zone of uplifts and 100 MT in hydrocarbon fields were reported. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 764816. This work is supported by the China Government (National Natural Science Foundation of China) under contract No.91434124 and No.51376105.

in the later studies for Lithuania (Šliaupienė and, Šliaupa, 2011, Haselton, 2013, CGS Baltic seed project (S81), 2017). Also additional offshore storage capacity could be added to these numbers, for example in offshore E7 structure, where average conservative-optimistic CO₂ storage capacity of 7-34 Mt were estimated (Shogenov et al, 2013).

Table 4.3: CO₂ storage capacity assessment in the studied countries

CO₂ storage capacity assessment in EU GeoCapacity Report/later studies (conservative estimates)						
Country	Saline aquifers, Mt	Hydrocarbon fields, Mt	Coal fields, Mt	Total capacity, Mt	Annual CO₂ emissions from large point sources (≥100000 tonnes), Mt	Years of storage
Italy	4669	1810	71	6550	140	47
Estonia	No capacity	No capacity	No capacity	No capacity	12	No capacity
Latvia	700	-	-	700	2	350
Lithuania	30/100	7/100	-	37/200	6	6/30
Russia (Kaliningrad Region)	NA	NA/33	NA	NA	NA	NA

In Kaliningrad Region of Russia total conservative capacity were estimated as 33 Mt CO₂ including onshore (29.1 Mt) and offshore storage potential (7 Mt) in the hydrocarbon fields (Šliaupa et al, 2013).

4.4 Monitoring requirements

Monitoring is one of the key activities required by the CCS Directive to ensure the safety of geological storage. The main requirements in the area are stated in Article 13, as follows.

“Member States shall ensure that the operator carries out monitoring of the injection facilities, the storage complex (including where possible the CO₂ plume), and where appropriate the surrounding environment for the purpose of:

- comparison between the actual and modelled behaviour of CO₂ and formation water, in the storage site;
- detecting significant irregularities;
- detecting migration of CO₂;
- detecting leakage of CO₂;
- detecting significant adverse effects for the surrounding environment, including in particular on drinking water, for human populations, or for users of the surrounding biosphere;
- assessing the effectiveness of any corrective measures taken pursuant to Article 16;
- updating the assessment of the safety and integrity of the storage complex in the short- and long-term, including the assessment of whether the stored CO₂ will be completely and permanently contained.

The monitoring shall be based on a monitoring plan designed by the operator. The plan shall be updated pursuant to the requirements laid down in Annex II and in any case every five years to take account of changes to the assessed risk of leakage, changes to the assessed risks to the environment and human health, new scientific knowledge, and improvements in best available technology. Updated plans shall be re-submitted for approval to the competent authority (Table 4.4).

Italian CCS Decree includes Annex I (analogue to Annex I to CCS directive about characterisation and assessment of the potential storage complex) and Annex II (criteria for establishing and updating the plan) analogue to the Annex II to CCS directive. The monitoring programme needs to be updated every five years in accordance with the provisions of this Description. Article 10 of the Law stipulates that the operator must monitor the CO₂ injection facilities and monitor the storage complex and the CO₂ accumulation and environment, where this is necessary. Chapter VI and Chapter VII of the Description states the procedures and provisions for the ‘Reporting Requirements for Operators’ and for the ‘Supervision of CO₂ Geological Storage Activity’, respectively. Both are in accordance with the provisions set out in Article 14 of the CCS Directive for Reporting and Article 15 of the Directive for Inspections (Decreto Legislativo n. 162, 2011).

Lithuania is applying the Order No 1-156 of the Deputy Director of the Geological Survey of Lithuania under the Ministry of Environment of 24 August 2011 on the approval of methodological requirements for the preparation of the part of the monitoring programme related to ground water monitoring which foresees: ‘51. In order to optimise the monitoring of injection facilities, CO₂ geological storage complex and the surrounding environment, it is advisable to follow the guidance document of the European Commission on the characterization of the storage complex, CO₂ stream composition, monitoring and corrective measures’. The monitoring programme will be prepared by the operator and agreed by the respective regional environmental department of the Ministry of Environment. A copy of

the agreed monitoring programme must be submitted to the Geological Survey of Lithuania. The operator should include full information on monitoring carried out in accordance with the guidelines adopted on the basis of Articles 14 and 23(2) of the Directive 2003/87/EC and agreed pursuant to Article 6(6)(4) of the Law and point 85.5 of the Description approved by the Lithuanian Government.

Table 4.4: EU and National Requirements for CO₂ Storage Site Monitoring

CO ₂ Storage Site Monitoring							
	During Storage			Post-closure period			
	Operator		Competent authority	Routine inspections by competent authority			Operational obligations
Country	Reporting to competent authority	Monitoring plan updating	Routine inspections	3 years after closure	Until transfer of responsibility (minimum 20 year)	After transfer of responsibility	
						Routine inspections	Financial contribution to monitoring costs
EU Directive	At least once a year	Every 5 years	At least once a year	At least once a year	Every 5 years	May be reduced, or intensified in case of problem	30 years
Italy	By 31 March of each year, Within 30 days in case of permit withdrawal	Every 5 years	At least once a year	At least once a year	At least every 5 years	May be reduced, or intensified in case of problem	30 years
Lithuania	At least once a year	Every 5 years	At least once a year	At least once a year	Every 5 years	May be reduced, or intensified in case of problem	30 years

In addition to the CCS Directive, monitoring will also need to meet the requirements under the European Union Emission Trading Scheme (EU ETS) and its Monitoring and Reporting Guidelines (MRG). The MRG are set out in relevant documents (Commission Decision 2007/589/EC on MRG; Commission Decision 2010/345/EU amending Commission Decision 2007/589/EC). In addition to the CCS Directive's requirement to detect leakage, the provisions under the EU ETS require that any leaked emissions that occur from storage activities are quantified and reported in order to determine the allowances that must be surrendered under the EU ETS and to monitor the effectiveness of CO₂ storage as a GHG mitigation technology.

Commission Decision 2010/345/EU amending Commission Decision 2007/589/EC is a basis for determining the emissions from CO₂ storage and transport in Estonia. This regulation also includes provisions for reporting, operators must submit an annual report to the Ministry of Environment of Estonia on the monitoring technology used and the quantities of CO₂ transported for storage during the reporting period. Additionally, operators must keep a record of the quantities and chemical content of the CO₂ transported, which should be sent to the Ministry of Environment once a year. Article 15 (including routine and non-routine inspections) is not applied in Estonia as there are no storage complexes or storage sites suitable for storing carbon dioxide as required by directive 2009/31/EC.

4.5 Third-party access to transport network and storage site and transboundary issues

Article 21 of CCS directive encourages Member States to take the measures enabling potential users to obtain access to transport networks and storage sites for the purpose of geological storage of captured CO₂. According to the CCS directive operators of transport networks and of storage sites “may refuse access on the grounds of lack of capacity. Duly substantiated reasons shall be given for any refusal.”

Article 24 of CCS Directive encourages transboundary cooperation for cases of transboundary transport of CO₂, transboundary storage site or transboundary storage complexes. For such cooperation competent authorities of the Member States shall jointly meet the requirements of the CCS Directive and other relevant EU legislations. The CCS directive encourages bilateral agreements between countries to arrange for transboundary CO₂ transport in order to circumvent the London Protocol prohibiting the export of CO₂ as waste (EC, 2009A).

Estonia has current legislative acts, regulating the construction of CO₂ transport networks. The construction of CO₂ transport pipelines underwater requires a permit, which is issued by the Minister of Environment according to the Water Act. This legislation also stipulates requirement for submerging a cable line under water and consent for this is granted by the Government. CO₂ transport pipeline that runs underground through several local

government areas is considered to be a linear structure, the corridor of which is established under country plans according to the Planning Act of Estonia. The Act Amending the Ambient Air Protection Act, stipulates the provisions for third-party access. A key provision states that ‘the owner or operator of the existing transport pipeline has an obligation to connect to the existing CO₂ transport pipeline by pipeline of another entity who has requested that (‘accessing entity’) if the technical conditions allow for it and it does not pose a risk to the existing transport capacity, people’s health or environment’. Any refusals must be explained in writing within 30 days of receiving the access application.

Latvia took the law in October 2011 “Arrangements for transporting carbon dioxide flows”, which includes issues on transport networks, pipelines, transboundary transport and CO₂ flow purity (not less than 96% CO₂). The law (consisting of four paragraphs) rules the procedure for the transport of carbon dioxide flows through pipelines to storage areas in geological structures, the purity criteria for carbon dioxide flows and the procedures for the review of access to transport networks and storage areas. The regulation is mainly dedicated to the “third-party access”, and only very shortly regulated transboundary transport, by requirement of cooperation of competent authorities of both bordering Member States.

It is stated that “The transport network operator shall provide a potential user of the transport network with access to the transport network for the transport of carbon dioxide streams through pipelines to areas where carbon dioxide storage is permitted...The operator of the transport network may deny access to the transport network, as a result of lack of capacity or connection”. Also cooperation between Member States is envisaged for the case when the transport network or the storage site is under the jurisdiction of two or more than two Member States. Latvia has experience in transboundary transport of natural gas (from Russia), and its underground storage and support when necessary to Estonia and Lithuania.

Lithuanian law on geological storage of carbon dioxide, taken on 28 June 2011 in Vilnius, includes Article 19 “The Republic of Lithuania international cooperation on CO₂ geological storage issues”, where in only five lines explained: “when the CO₂ transported in more than one Member State of the EU or when the storage or a storage complex is located in more than one Member State of the EU, then Republic of Lithuania together with competent authorities of other EU Member States shall comply with the requirements laid down in the EU legislation on the geological storage of CO₂. Article 20 of Lithuanian law “Access to the pipeline and storage facilities” is explaining the procedure of giving the access, or refusing the access if there is not enough capacity (Valstybės žinios, 2011a).

Italian CCS Decree in Article 28 obliges operators of CO₂ transport networks and storage sites to guarantee the connection and free access to its transportation network and storage sites to other operators in the transparent and non-discriminatory manner. However, it is also stated that “transport network operators and operators of storage sites may refuse access for lack of ability or link”. Transnational cooperation is regulated only in short by Article 30 of Italian CCS Decree: “For cross-border transport of CO₂ storage sites or transboundary storage complexes, the Ministry of economic development and the Ministry of environment

shall fulfil the provisions of this Decree and other applicable Community standards, or promote the conclusion of agreements with countries outside the European Union”.

5. PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION OF CCS

Among studied countries only Italy made steps for practical implementation of CCS and have planned several projects (Rütters et al, 2013) which however were not practically implemented. The most interesting for the CLEANKER project is the planned by ENI feasibility study and pilot project of injection into a depleted hydrocarbon field. ENI has run various studies and preliminary evaluations as part of the design of surface infrastructure for CO₂ injection and monitoring in the Cortemaggiore field (Piacenza) and analysed the legal and societal aspects linked to storage here. The injection of 8000 tonnes of CO₂ per year was planned over a three-year period, followed by two years of post injection monitoring. Studies on the utilization of the CO₂ were also planned also be run in order to increase the recovery factor from Italian hydrocarbon fields (Rütters et al, 2013).

6. ASSESSMENT OF NATIONAL CCS REGULATIONS BY GCCSI

In 2015 the Global Carbon Capture and Storage Institute (GCCSI) estimated national legal and regulatory regimes for carbon capture and storage in 55 countries (GCCSI, 2015).

Primary Assessment Criteria applied in this assessment:

- 1 - The clarity and efficiency of the administrative process under the CCS legal framework to apply for, and obtain, regulatory approval for CCS projects
- 2 - The comprehensiveness of the legal framework in providing for all aspects of a CCS project, including siting, design, capture, transport, storage, closure and monitoring for potential releases of stored CO₂
- 3 - The extent to which the CCS legal and regulatory framework provides for the appropriate siting of projects and adequate environmental impact assessment processes
- 4 - The extent to which the CCS legal and regulatory framework provides for and incorporates meaningful and effective stakeholder and public consultation
- 5 - The way in which laws and regulations deal with long-term liability for closure, monitoring and accidental releases of CO₂.

Among five countries assessed in this report, no one was assigned into Band A (Table 6.1) estimated by GCCSI as representing “CCS-specific laws or existing laws that are applicable across most parts of the CCS project cycle”.

Italy and Lithuania A were assigned into Band B (CCS-specific laws or existing laws that are applicable across parts of the CCS project cycle).

Estonia, Latvia and Russia were assigned into Band C (very few CCS-specific or existing laws that are applicable across parts of the CCS project cycle) (Table 6.1).

Table 6.1: GCCSI Assessment Score (GCCSI, 2015)

Country	1	2	3	4	5	Band	
						B	C
Italy	7	25	10	6.5	8	56.5	
Estonia	7	8.5	9	4	2.5		31
Latvia	5	9	11.5	3.5	3		32
Lithuania	6	20	12.5	5	8	49.5	
Russia	6	9.5	10	4.5	3		33

7. EUROPEAN UNION EMISSION TRADING SYSTEM (EU ETS)

EU ETS was previously known as the EU Emissions Trading Scheme. The scheme currently has three operating phases (EU ETS, 2018):

- *Phase I* ran from 1 January 2005 to 31 December 2007 and was a 'learning by doing phase';
- *Phase II* runs from 1 January 2008 to 31 December 2012 and includes revised monitoring and reporting rules, more stringent emissions caps and additional combustion sources;
- *Phase III*, which runs from 1 January 2013 to 31 December 2020, brings major changes including, harmonised allocation methodologies and additional greenhouse gases and emission sources.

Installations covered by the EU ETS are those which carry out activities listed in Annex I of the EU ETS Directive. These include energy activities, production and processing of ferrous metals, mineral industries and pulp and paper industries. Launched in 2005, the EU ETS works on the "cap and trade" principle. This means there is a "cap", or limit, on the total amount of certain greenhouse gases that can be emitted by the factories, power plants and other installations in the system. Within this cap, companies receive emission allowances which they can sell to or buy from one another as needed. The limit on the total number of allowances available ensures that they have a value.

At the end of each year each company must surrender enough allowances to cover all its emissions, otherwise heavy fines are imposed. If a company reduces its emissions, it can keep the spare allowances to cover its future needs or else sell them to another company that is short of allowances. The flexibility that trading brings ensures that emissions are cut where it costs least to do so. The EU ETS has proved that putting a price on carbon and trading in it can work. Emissions from installations in the system are falling as intended – by slightly over 8% compared to the beginning of phase 3. In 2020, emissions from sectors covered by the system will be 21% lower than in 2005. In 2030, under the revised system they will be 43% lower. The 2013 cap for emissions from stationary installations was set at

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2 084 301 856 allowances. This cap decreases each year by a linear reduction factor of 1.74% of the average total quantity of allowances issued annually in 2008-2012, thus ensuring that the number of allowances that can be used by stationary installations will be 21% lower in 2020 than in 2005.

The EU ETS now operates in 31 countries (the 28 EU Member States plus Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway). As of 2013 it covers CO₂ emissions from 11000 power plants and manufacturing installations and slightly over 500 aircraft operators flying between EEA's airports. It covers around 45% of the EU's GHG emissions.

As of Phase 3 (2013-2020), the sectors with stationary installations regulated by the EU ETS are energy intensive industries, including power stations and other combustion plants with >20MW thermal rated input (except hazardous or municipal waste installations), oil refineries, coke ovens, iron and steel, cement clinker, glass, lime, bricks, ceramics, pulp, paper and board, aluminium, petrochemicals, ammonia, nitric, adipic, glyoxal and glyoxylic acid production, CO₂ capture, transport in pipelines and geological storage of CO₂.

Until June 2017, allocation has been reduced by around 301.9 million allowances due to installations that have closed or reduced their production or their production capacity compared to the one initially used to calculate Phase 3 allocation.

The EU ETS covers CO₂ emissions, nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions from all nitric, adipic, glyoxylic acid and glyoxal production, and perfluorocarbons (PFC) emissions from aluminium production. Even though participation in the EU ETS is mandatory, in some sectors only installations above a certain size are included.

The EU ETS has put a price on carbon emissions and shown that it is possible to trade in greenhouse gas emissions. Emissions from installations in the scheme are falling as intended. The success of the EU ETS has inspired other countries and regions to launch cap and trade schemes of their own. Other countries and regions are now developing similar systems.

In July 2015, the European Commission presented a legislative proposal for the revision (EC, 2015b) of the EU ETS for the fourth trading period (i.e. 2021-2030). The proposed changes include an increase in the pace of emissions cuts (the overall number of allowances will decline at an annual rate of 2.2% from 2021 onwards, compared with 1.74% currently), the better targeted and more dynamic allocation of free allowances, and several support mechanisms to help the industry and power sectors meet the innovation and investment challenges of the transition to a low-carbon economy.

National installations registered in 2015 in EU ETS produced 143635 kt of CO₂ in Italy, 10996, 1714 and 6028 kt of CO₂ in Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania correspondingly (Table 7.1).

During 2015-2017 registered in EU ETS emissions did not decreased in Italy, they significantly increased in Estonia (about 20% during 2016-2017), but they decreased in Latvia. In Lithuania 2014-2016 decrease stopped in 2017 and increased for about 2% (Table 7.2).

Table 7.1: EU ETS national data in 2015 (EEA, 2017)

Country	Fuel consumption (TJ)	CO ₂ emissions (kt)	Number of registered installations				
			< 25 000 t CO ₂ -eq	25 000 – 50 000 t CO ₂ -eq	50 000 – 500 000 t CO ₂ -eq	>500 000 t CO ₂ -eq	In total
Italy	2078031	143635	-	744	234	93	1071
Estonia	106 684	10996	28	5	8	4	45
Latvia	30173	1714	56	4	2	2	64
Lithuania	99940	6028	78	3	6	3	90

Table 7.2: CO₂ Emissions from industrial installations as a percentage of the previous year (EU ETS, 2018)

Country	2014	2015	2016	2017
Italy	92.78	102.24	99.22	100.16
Estonia	94.08	79.52	112.49	109.22
Latvia	89.67	101.03	95.78	94.87
Lithuania	91.41	99.79	90.32	101.92

7.4 Monitoring and Reporting Guidelines

The Monitoring and Reporting Guidelines (MRG) under the ETS Directive (Commission Decision 2007/589/EC and its amendment Commission Decision 2010/345/EU) provide monitoring and reporting guidelines for greenhouse gas emissions from the capture, transport and geological storage of CO₂. The MRG specify how emissions of the CO₂ storage activity have to be accounted for and reported for purposes of the EU ETS (MRG Annexes I (e.g. Section 4.3) and XVIII).

The following emission sources at a storage site have to be monitored under the EU ETS:

- Combustion emissions at the injection site;
- Fugitive emissions and emissions from venting at the injection site;
- Emissions from vents and flaring at enhanced hydrocarbon recovery;

- Leakage from the storage reservoir into the water column or atmosphere;
The MRG places emphasis on the verification, accounting and reporting of any emissions (i.e., quantification), the relevant content of which is given below. In the MRG one of the guiding principles is to minimize the uncertainty in the quantification of emissions.

8. INTEGRATION OF EU ETS AND EU CCS DIRECTIVE

Some monitoring methods used for monitoring under the CCS Directive may be suitable for quantification of any emissions resulting from leakage. Furthermore, quantification of any leakage will be useful in assessing the significance of the leakage risk as required under the CCS Directive.

Monitoring activities and plans need to meet the requirements of the CCS Directive should be extended to meet the requirements of the MRG under the EU ETS. It will be more efficient for both the operator and the competent authority of a storage site to set up and manage monitoring on an integrated basis, covering both CCS and EU ETS issues.

Emissions sources at the injection site and from enhanced hydrocarbon recovery can be monitored using existing approaches from the MRG. Combustion emissions at injection can be monitored with approaches from Annex II (stationary combustion), vented emissions at injection and at enhanced hydrocarbon recovery with approaches from Annex XII (continuous emission measurement) and fugitive emissions at injection by industry best practice. For the MRG formats for monitoring plans already exist at Member State level. This includes industry best practice approaches.

9. REGULATIONS FOR CO₂ USE

8 June 2010 EC amended Decision 2007/589/EC to include monitoring and reporting guidelines for greenhouse gas emissions from capture, transport and geological storage (EC, 2010). Some CO₂ use issues are also included in this regulation.

In the Annex 1 to this decision

- “enhanced hydrocarbon recovery” is determined as the recovery of hydrocarbons in addition to those extracted by water injection or other means.
- Where leakages from storage complex are identified and lead to emissions, or release of CO₂ to the water column, they shall be included as emissions sources for the respective installation and shall be monitored accordingly as required in Annex XVII.

Section 5.7 is replaced by the “5.7 Transferred CO₂”:

Subject to approval by the competent authority, the operator may subtract from the calculated level of emissions of the installation any CO₂ which is not emitted from the installation, but transferred out of the installation:

- as pure substance, or directly used and bound in products or as feedstock, or
- to another installation holding a greenhouse gas emissions permit, unless other requirements as set out in Annexes XVII or XVIII apply,

provided the subtraction is mirrored by a respective reduction for the activity and installation, which the respective Member State reports in its national inventory submission to the Secretariat of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. The respective amounts of CO₂ shall be reported for each installation CO₂ has been transferred to or received from as a memo item in the annual emission report of the transferring as well as the receiving installation.

In the case of transfer to another installation, the receiving installation must add to its calculated level of emissions the received CO₂, unless other requirements as set out in Annexes XVII or XVIII apply.

Respective transferring as well as receiving installations shall be notified by Member States to the Commission pursuant to Article 21 of Directive 2003/87/EC. In case of transfer to an installation falling under that Directive, the transferring installation shall identify the receiving installation in its annual emission report by stating the receiving installation's installation identification code as defined by the Regulation pursuant to Article 19 of that Directive. The receiving installation shall identify the transferring installation through the same approach.

Potential cases of transferred CO₂ out of an installation include, inter alia:

- pure CO₂ used for the carbonation of beverages,
- pure CO₂ used as dry ice for cooling purposes,
- pure CO₂ used as fire extinguishing agent, refrigerant or as laboratory gas,
- pure CO₂ used for grains disinfections,
- pure CO₂ used as solvent in the food or chemical industry,
- CO₂ used and bound in products or feedstocks in the chemical, pulp industry (e.g. for urea or precipitated carbonates),
- carbonates bound in spray-dried absorption product (SDAP) from semi-dry scrubbing of flue gases,
- CO₂ transferred to capture installations,
- CO₂ from capture installations transferred to transport networks,
- CO₂ from transport networks transferred to storage sites.

Unless other requirements in the activity specific Annexes apply, the mass of annually transferred CO₂ or carbonate shall be determined with a maximum uncertainty of less than 1,5 % either directly by using volume or mass flow meters, weighing or indirectly from the mass of the respective product (e.g. carbonates or urea) where relevant and if appropriate.

In case the amounts of transferred CO₂ are measured both at the transferring and at the receiving installation, the amounts of respectively transferred and received CO₂ shall be identical. If the deviation between measured values is in a range, which can be explained by the uncertainty of the measurement systems, the arithmetic average of both measured values shall be used in both the transferring and receiving installations' emission reports. The emission report shall include a statement that this value has been aligned with the value of

the respectively transferring or receiving installation. The measured value shall be included as memo item.

9.1 CO₂ use for EOR

EU has adopted rules in the CCS Directive (EC, 2009a) regarding the geological storage of CO₂ (“injection accompanied by storage of CO₂ streams in underground geological formations”) in the Member States in the CCS Directive. Under the CCS Directive the Member States have the right to determine the areas where storage sites may be selected and, therefore, to decide whether or not they will allow CCS. Where the Member States allow CCS, the directive sets the legal framework for such activities. The term EOR is not addressed by the CCS Directive. The CCS Directive includes Preamble Recital 20:

“Enhanced Hydrocarbon Recovery (EHR) refers to the recovery of hydrocarbons in addition to those extracted by water injection or other means. EHR is not in itself included in the scope of this Directive. However, where EHR is combined with geological storage of CO₂, the provisions of this Directive for the environmentally safe storage of CO₂ should apply. In that case, the provisions of this Directive concerning leakage are not intended to apply to quantities of CO₂ released from surface installations, which do not exceed what is necessary in the normal process of extraction of hydrocarbons, and which do not compromise the security of the geological storage or adversely affect the surrounding environment. Such releases are covered by the inclusion of storage sites in Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 October 2003 establishing a scheme for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the Community (EC, 2003), which requires surrender of emissions trading allowances for any leaked emissions.” (EC, 2011). Pure CO₂-EOR operations involving incidental storage (including temporary storage connected with buffering operations) would not qualify as storage under the directive, but as an inevitable and ordinary result of EOR operations: the directive does not apply.

There are some other gaps exist in the Directive:

- 1) CO₂ stream shall consist overwhelmingly of carbon dioxide. ‘Overwhelmingly’ is a flexible standard.
- 2) No waste or other matter may be added for the purpose of disposing of that waste or other matter (art 12 Directive). Substances from CCS-EOR activities will not be ‘added’ but ‘returned’.
- 3) “incidental associated substances from the source, capture or injection process”- below levels that affect integrity of storage site; pose significant environmental and health risk; are in breach of the EU law - are allowed. Ultimate objective is the environmental integrity of the site.
- 4) Transport: To be considered as not emitted, CO₂ must be transferred to specific receiving installations: a capture installation for the purpose of transport or storage; a transport network or a storage site (2012 regulation, art 49). “Transport network” under

the CCS Directive: “the network of pipelines, including associated booster stations, for the transport of CO₂ to the storage site”. Transfer to a ship is not covered to this purpose. However, the Preamble does not have binding legal force, cannot serve as a ground for derogating from the main body of the relevant act, whilst may be used to “cast light on the interpretation to be given to a legal rule, it cannot in itself constitute such a rule”. But no EOR provision to be interpreted in the Directive, so the Preamble has somewhat of an “orphan status”. The recital refers to a formal exception in the proposed directive art 2(1) subsequently dropped following strong opposition in 2008.

During the past 40 years nearly 1 Gt of CO₂ has been injected into geological reservoirs as part of CO₂-EOR activities. CO₂-EOR is considered a means for advancing the deployment of large-scale CO₂ storage projects due to its commercial advantages over dedicated storage prospects (GCCSI, 2013).

Enhanced oil recovery (EOR) is able to store significant amounts of CO₂ (CO₂-EOR), while at the same time increasing oil production by on average 13%, which has a significant economic value. Moreover, oil and gas reservoirs are prime candidates for CO₂ storage for several reasons. First, the oil and gas that originally accumulated in traps did not escape, demonstrating the safety and reliability of such storage sites, provided that their structural integrity was not compromised as a result of exploration and extraction processes. Second, the geological structure and physical properties of most oil and gas fields have been extensively studied and characterized. Third, existing fields' geology and characteristics are well known to the oil and gas industry to predict the movement, displacement behaviour and trapping of gases and liquids (EC, 2013).

As for a depleted oil and gas field, there should be production data and a history matching of the produced fluids available, which will allow good predictions as to the reservoir performance for the injection of CO₂. EOR activities of production and injection may have resulted in damage to the reservoirs and seals during production which may lead to geomechanical failure. As many wells may have been converted from hydrocarbon producers to injectors and/or hydrocarbon and CO₂ producers, they will have had a longer life of maintenance and management, and so will need to be thoroughly assessed as to their ongoing suitability for geological storage of CO₂ from a materials and engineering failure perspective. There are examples of CO₂ blow outs due to materials failures in CO₂-EOR fields (EC, 2011).

Almost all the CO₂-EOR projects are in the US with very few projects in other countries. Due to the potential of EOR in Europe is limited, no one European country has implemented their national regulations for CO₂-EOR (EC Communication, 2013). However, one CO₂-EOR pilot injection was successfully conducted in Lithuania with significant results of 40% of enhanced oil recovery (Haselton, 2013).

In Energy strategy of Russian Federation to 2030 the gas, gas-water, thermal-gas, EOR-gas-chemical and thermal EOR methods were identified as priorities. “Energy Strategy 2030” forms a number of target indicators of oil production technological advancement, such as

scaling up the implementation of industrial innovative technologies, enhanced oil recovery and intensified oil production (Cherepovitsyn and Ilinova, 2016)

Commission decision of 8 June 2010 amending Decision 2007/589/EC as regards the inclusion of monitoring and reporting guidelines for greenhouse gas emissions from the capture, transport and geological storage of carbon dioxide (notified under document C(2010) 3310) includes Annex XVIII “Activity-specific guidelines for the geological storage of CO₂ in a storage site permitted under Directive 2009/31/EC.

In paragraph 2.3 “Vented and fugitive emissions from enhanced hydrocarbon recovery operations” it is stated:

The combination of EHR with geological storage of CO₂ is likely to provide an additional source stream of emissions, namely the breakthrough of CO₂ with the produced hydrocarbons. Additional emission sources from EHR operations include:

- the oil-gas separation units and gas recycling plant, where fugitive emissions of CO₂ could occur,
- the flare stack, where emissions might occur due to the application of continuous positive purge systems and during depressurisation of the hydrocarbon production installation,
- the CO₂ purge system, to avoid that high concentrations of CO₂ extinguish the flare.

Any fugitive emissions occurring will usually be rerouted in a gas containment system, to the flare or CO₂ purge system. Any such fugitive emissions or CO₂ vented e.g. from the CO₂ purge system shall be determined in accordance to Section 2.2 of the Annex. Emissions from the flare stack shall be determined in accordance with Annex II, taking into account potential inherent CO₂ in the flare gas.

Monitoring shall start in the case that any leakage results in emissions or release to the water column. Emissions resulting from a release of CO₂ into the water column shall be deemed to be equal to the amount released to the water column.

Monitoring of emissions or of release into the water column from a leakage shall continue until corrective measures pursuant to Article 16 of Directive 2009/31/EC have been taken and emissions or release into the water column can no longer be detected”.

9.2 CO₂ use for Geothermal Energy Recovery (CO₂-GER)

CO₂ could be used for Geothermal Energy Recovery as more effective fluid than water. Using geologic CO₂ storage for enhanced geothermal energy and water recovery and energy storage may generate enough revenues to compensate for (or to even exceed) CO₂ capture and storage costs.

The use of supercritical CO₂ as a working fluid in geothermal systems was first proposed for EGS in low-permeability, hot crystalline basement rocks (Pruess, 2006). CO₂ plume geothermal (CPG) differs from CO₂-EGS, because CPG extracts heat from sedimentary or stratigraphic reservoirs that have naturally high permeability and are much larger than the artificially generated EGS reservoirs. CPG could be also combined with CCS (CO₂ Capture and Storage) and enhanced hydrocarbon recovery (Randolph and Saar, 2011). Recently it is

proposed to use CO₂ geological storage for geothermal energy production and grid-scale energy storage in deep sedimentary reservoirs (3–5 km) sealed and overlaid by impermeable cap and bedrocks (Buscheck et al, 2016 a, b).

However, this technology is only at the research and development phase in Europe and close to demonstration phase in USA (Buscheck et al, 2016, Randolph and Saar, 2011). Considering that using CO₂ for GER is very prospective in such countries like Italy and it can save water resources, we are going to consider this technology for the CLEANKER CCUS scenarios.

9.2.1 Renewable Energy Directive

The Renewable Energy Directive (Directive 2009/28/EC) is a central element of the Energy Union policy and a key driver for providing clean energy for all Europeans, in view of making the EU world number one in renewables while contributing to the five dimensions of the Energy Union. Renewables have played a major role in energy security. Their estimated contribution to fossil fuel import savings in 2015 was €16 bln and it is projected to be €58 bln in 2030. Thanks to fast decreasing costs owing to technological advancement, especially in the power sector, renewables can also be gradually further integrated in the market. The state of play of the availability of facilitated administrative procedures in EU Member States in 2014 (Table 9.1) is reported by EC recently (EC, 2017b).

The recast of the Renewables Directive for the period after 2020 together with the Market Design proposals as part of the Clean Energy for all Europeans package will further enable renewables participation on equal footing with other energy sources. Renewables also walk hand and hand with energy efficiency. In the electricity sector, fuel-switching from combustible fossil fuels to non-combustible renewables could reduce primary energy consumption. In the building sector, renewables solutions can improve the energy performance of building in a cost-effective way. Renewables are also a crucial driver for the decarbonisation of the Union's energy system. In 2015, renewables contributed to gross avoided greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions of the equivalent of the emissions of Italy. Last but not least, renewables play a major role in making the EU a global leader on innovation. With 30% of global patents in renewables, the EU has been a pioneer in this field, and is committed to prioritise research and innovation to further drive the energy transition (EC, 2009Ab, EC, 2017b).

The Renewable Energy Directive (EC, 2009b) lays down a binding objective of achieving the proportion of 10% of renewable fuels in final transport sector fuel consumption in the European Union member states by 2020.

According to Eurostat, (2017) 11 EU countries already reached 2020 renewable energy targets, including Italy, Estonia and Lithuania.

Italy. The 2017 National Energy Strategy, the most relevant recent issue in the Italian energy, was adopted by the Ministry of Economic Development and the Ministry of the Environment and of the Protection of the Territory and of the Sea. It sets 10-year targets

for specific energy sectors/areas. The strategy fixed three pillars for the Italian energy sector, including the third pillar Environment with its overcoming 2030 European environmental targets, in line with the COP21 and Road Map 2050 objectives through the decarbonisation of the energy system and the phasing out of coal starting from 2025. This strategy includes by 2030 total energy share of renewables 28% and 55% share of renewable in electricity production (Table 9.2).

Estonia. Estonia has been a member of the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) since 2011. Estonia increasingly focus on environmentally-friendly production and consumption. (<https://www.mkm.ee>). In October 2017, the Government confirmed the Estonian Energy Development Plan until 2030 (ENMAK, 2017), the main objective of which is to ensure the availability of energy supplies to consumers and the best possible price. Among major objectives of ENMAK by 2030 is the share of renewable energy increases and accounts for 50% of final energy consumption, renewable energy generation works without subsidies and achieves 50% of final consumption of domestic electricity, 80% of the heat generated in Estonia is produced from renewable energy sources (Table 9.2), (ENMAK, 2017).

Table 9.1: State of play of the availability of facilitated administrative procedures in EU Member States in 2014 (renewables) (EC, 2017b)

Country	One Stop Shop	Online application	Maximum time limit for procedures	Automatic permission after deadline	Facilitated procedures for small scale producers	Identification of geographical sites
Italy	existing	absent	existing	absent	existing	absent
Estonia	absent	existing	existing	existing	absent	absent
Latvia	absent	absent	existing	absent	absent	absent
Lithuania	absent	existing	existing	existing	existing	No data

The Latvian Energy Long Term Strategy 2030 sets a target of 50% share of renewable energy in the mix and a reduction of 50% of energy imports.

Lithuania. The goal of Lithuania is to reach a 30 % share of renewable energy sources (RES) in the final energy consumption by 2020. In the next three years, the installed power of wind energy will increase by 50 %, and that of solar twice. It is planned that by 2030 RES installed power will be 2.5 times what it is now, and almost half (45%) of the consumed energy should be manufactured from renewable sources; by 2050 energy from renewable and other non-polluting sources will comprise the majority of energy used in the electricity, heating, and transport sectors. By 2050, all electricity – and all heating in the district heating sector – should be produced from RES, while in the transportation sector RES energy will amount to 50% (Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Lithuania, 2018).

In 2018, the negotiation process for the European Union’s post-2020 climate and energy framework is coming to an end. The new regulatory framework includes a binding renewable energy target for the EU for 2030 of 32% with an upwards revision clause by 2023 (EC, 2018b). The discussion had recognised geothermal as a relevant energy source for the future of Europe (EGEC, 2018).

Table 9.2: Share of energy from renewable sources (in % of gross final energy consumption)

Country	2014	2015	2016	2017	2020 target	2030 target, % Total energy/ electricity heating
Italy	17.1	17.5	17.4		17	28/55/NA
Estonia	26.3	28.6	28.8		25	50/50/80
Latvia	38.7	37.6	37.2		40	50/NA/NA
Lithuania	23.6	25.8	25.6		23/30*	50/50*
Russia	NA	3.3	NA	NA	NA	NA

9.2.2 Geothermal Energy

Geothermal is becoming more and more attractive as a competitive renewable heating source (EGEC, 2016). With output approximated at 0.7 Mtoe in 2015, geothermal deployment is below the NREAPs anticipated trajectory. Due to their high natural potential, three countries (Italy, France and Hungary) are leading the European geothermal production. The slow deployment of this technology is mainly due to very high capital expenditures (EC, 2017b). Today geothermal power plants reached a capacity of 2.85 GW (EGEC, 2018). In 2015, geothermal energy represented 3.1 % of the EU’s total primary renewable energy production. The installed capacity in the EU is divided into: 16 GW in ground source heat pumps; around 3.8 GW in direct use; and 1 GW in geothermal power plants. Geothermal resources are currently being exploited to only a limited degree, especially considering the enormous technical potential, estimated at about 2 600 TW by 2050 (EC, 2017b).

A substantial number of projects have been developed throughout Europe, and geothermal energy is on its way to become a key player in the European energy market. Increasing the use of geothermal energy and strengthening the geothermal industrial sector, will allow a

substantial reduction of CO₂ emissions, the saving of primary energy, and the creation and sustainment of a work force with considerable skill levels (EC, 2017b).

The first regions to install geothermal heat systems in Europe (Iceland, France, Hungary) were those with the best hydrothermal potential. Systems can be small (from 0.5 to 2 MW) or large, with capacity of 50 MW. In 2018, around 300 geothermal district heating systems are in operation, and thousands of applications for the agri-food industry, fish farming, balneology or recreational and leisure, are running based on geothermal. Around 20% of the EU population is located in regions where the temperature at 2000 m deep is higher than 60°C, so are directly suitable for geothermal heating and cooling. The potential of shallow geothermal energy is also significant. Shallow geothermal energy is available everywhere. More than 2 million units of shallow geothermal systems are installed in Europe today (EGEC, 2018).

In November 2016, the European Union made a clear commitment to achieve global leadership in renewable energies and put energy efficiency first. To deliver this ambition, the legislative framework must encourage both the large-scale rapid deployment of renewable energy and energy efficiency measures, and the uptake of small-scale, local citizen and community owned distributed renewable energy and highly efficient cogeneration installations (EGEC, 2018).

Geothermal fosters local economic development through many indirect positive effects, such as jobs creation and air quality. In the power sector, it will be a stabilizer ensuring security of supply for the grid and the society. Geothermal power plants could be developed in all European regions. This should be taken into account in the current reform of the market design, adding a regional dimension between the centralised and decentralized approaches. The structure of the heating and cooling sector is more complex than the one for electricity, but geothermal has a key role to play for its decarbonisation. From the many technologies and sources available, the market will decide the optimal mix of energy sources for each region. Together with other renewables, geothermal will offer solutions for a clean, competitive and secure heating, cooling and domestic hot water for buildings and the industry through major technologies such as geothermal district heating systems and industrial applications (EGEC, 2018).

Italy is one of the world's leading countries in terms of geothermal resources. Geothermal resources are mainly utilised for electricity production, and all plants are located in the region of Tuscany, specifically Larderello-Travale and Mount Amiata. In 2013, Enel Green Power installed the first binary power plant in Italy, Gruppo Binario Bangore 3 of 1 MW. In 2015, Cornia 2 power plant has been upgraded with the integration of biomass fired boiler (using local forest biomass) to raise geothermal steam temperatures from about 150°C to 380°C. This hybridisation added 5 MW of capacity to the plant and output is expected to increase by 30 GW per year (WEC, 2018).

Lithuania's geothermal resource, lying in the west of the country, has been found to be significant. In 2000 the 41 MW (18 MW geothermal heat and 23 MW heat from absorption

heat pump driven boilers) Klaipeda Geothermal Demonstration Plant (KGDP) was commissioned and began producing 25% of the heat required by the city of Klaipeda. Much work has been undertaken on the thermal waters in Vilkaviskis, a city in the south-western part of the country, with a view to developing balneological uses and also a district heating scheme. To date, Lithuania’s extensive low-temperature resource has been harnessed for an estimated 1 000 ground-source heat pumps, with an installed capacity of 17 MW (WEC, 2018).

Table 9.3: Installed capacity and production for geothermal electricity and district heating in 2016 (WEC, 2018)

Country	INSTALLED CAPACITY			PRODUCTION		
	Electricity generation, MW	Direct use, MW	Total capacity, MW	Electricity generation, ktoe per year	District use, ktoe per year	Total production, ktoe per year
Italy	824	1010	1834	509	207	716
Estonia	0	63	63	0	8.5	8.5
Latvia	0	1.63	1.63	0	0.76	0.76
Lithuania	14	80.6	94.6	2	15	17
Russia	78	308	386	39.1	147	186.1

9.3 CO₂ USE FOR CARBONATION OF HASARDOUS WASTES

9.3.1 Regulations for Hazardous Wastes

1. *The Waste Framework Directive*

The Waste Framework Directive lays down a strict control regime for hazardous waste. The Directive stipulates that hazardous waste must be recorded, identified and kept separated from other types of hazardous and non-hazardous waste. The properties which render waste hazardous are laid down in the Directive and are further specified by Decision 2000/532/EC establishing a List of Wastes (EC, 2000).

Italy generated in 2014 considerable amount of hazardous waste in three categories W012, W121 and W124 with correspondingly 6, 3 and 9 kg per capita. Estonia produces around 8.6 mln tonnes of hazardous combustion waste per year (mainly oil shale ash), corresponding to 6600 tonnes of hazardous waste per capita. These numbers of the produced total combustion wastes are 15 times higher than in Italy, and 700 times higher than per capita in Italy (Table 9.4).

In 2014 Latvia generated low amount of hazardous waste in three categories W012, W121 and W124 which are the lowest in the studied countries (Table 9.4). Lithuania has generated

in 2014 considerable amount of hazardous waste in category W012, with correspondingly 2 kg per capita. In category W121 its waste was insignificant and the lowest among the studied EU countries.

Table 9.4: Mineral and solidified hazardous waste from mining and quarrying (EUROSTAT, 2018)

Generation of waste by waste category, 2014, Eurostat						
Country	W012- Acid, alkaline or saline waste, tonnes	W121- Mineral waste from construction and demolition, tonnes	W124 – Combustion wastes, tonnes	W012- Acid, alkaline or saline waste, kg per capita	W121- Mineral waste from construc- tion and demolition, kg per capita	W124 – Combus- tion wastes, kg per capita
Italy	376 659	207 820	548 299	6	3	9
Estonia	2 601	9 861	8 684 445	2	8	6606
Latvia	568	414	152	0	0	0
Lithuania	4 819	218	1 301	2	0	0

2. *The Landfill Directive*

The Landfill Directive banned co-disposal of waste which in practice means that hazardous waste must be assigned to a hazardous waste landfill (and municipal waste must go to a landfill for non-hazardous waste).

3. *The Basel Convention*

The Basel Convention on the Control of Transboundary Movements of Hazardous Wastes and their Disposal is an international treaty which came into force in 1992 having been signed by 172 Parties. It is designed to protect human health and the environment from potential adverse effects of hazardous wastes, through the control of transboundary movements and disposal of hazardous wastes. The driving force for drafting and adopting the Basel Convention was to prevent shipments of hazardous waste from developed to less developed countries, a practice which had begun to take place as authorized disposal routes had become more expensive as a consequence of environmental regulations becoming stricter.

9.4 CO₂ mineral carbonation using oil shale ash waste in Estonia

Processing of oil shale from mining to energy generates large amounts of different waste. Part of waste comes from power stations in a form of ash. Burning 1t of oil shale gives approximately 0.45t of hazardous alkaline ash (contains up to 50% CaO and 15% MgO) waste (Riigikogu, 2016, 2018). Ash alkalinity makes it possible to use it for CO₂ mineral carbonation – a potential future option for CO₂ sequestration for those EU member states which do not have sufficient geological storage capacity (Uibu et al, 2010).

9.4.1 EU Waste Directive, Waste Act

The EU Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC) has been transposed into Estonian legislation through the Waste Act (RT I 2004, 9, 52), adopted in 2004, and its subsequent amendments (the most recent one in 2018) as well as subordinated regulations (EC, 2008, Riigikogu, 2018).

There are no specific regulations for oil shale, except § 29. (Environmental impact of waste handling and best available techniques) states that (4) The minister responsible for the area shall have the right to issue regulations to implement the provisions of subsections (1)–(3) of this section and establish handling requirements for: (5) waste from thermal processing (including pyrolysis) of oil shale;

The minister responsible for the area has the right to establish, by a regulation, a detailed list of the waste resulting from products of concern in compliance with the waste list prepared on the basis of subsection 2 (4) of this Act if this is necessary in order to specify the waste and to enter the recovery data in the register or products of concern.

According to regulation of Minister of the Environment (RT I, 18.12.2015, 14), oil shale bottom ash and oil shale flow ash are listed as hazardous waste with codes 10 01 97* and 10 01 98* respectively (Riigikogu, 2016).

The Waste Act does not include specific rules for oil shale ash waste management, but lays down the general rules that should apply for the management of waste according to the waste hierarchy, as presented in the WFD (2008/98/EC) (EC, 2008).

9.4.2 National Waste Management Plan 2014-2020

Estonia has a National Waste Management Plan (WMP) for the period 2014-2020 (Keskkonnaministeerium, 2014). A chapter of the new WMP is dedicated to the development of the national Waste Prevention Plan, according to provisions stated in the WFD (2008/98/EC). The WMP places specific focus on the promotion and intensification of support for investments and financing to companies engaged in waste recycling in order to enhance their performance and treatment capacity with the aim of contributing to the achievement of both recovery/recycling targets of the WFD. The goal of Estonia, as described in the WMP, is to reduce land-filling as much (as possible and recover the highest

possible share of wastes. Oil shale ash is considered as a priority waste stream in the WMP of Estonia.

9.4.3 Industrial Emissions Act

To achieve a high level of protection of the environment taken as a whole by minimizing emissions into air, water and soil and the generation of waste the process of using oil shale for energy production is regulated by the Industrial Emissions Act (RT I, 16.05.2013, 1) (Riigikogu, 2017a). Act determines the industrial activities of high environmental hazard, provides the requirements for operation therein and liability for failure to comply with the requirements, and the organisation of state supervision. For that an integrated environmental permit system is used. Integrated permits are issued by the Environmental Board. The Environmental Inspectorate shall control by supervision the compliance of installations required to hold integrated permits with the requirements of the integrated permit and compliance of the activities of the installations with the requirements established in this Act and legislation established on the basis thereof.

9.4.4 Reusing of oil shale ash

To simplify the re-usage of oil shale ash, Eesti Energia has created a Material Safety Data Sheet for Oil Shale Thermal Processing Residue with the following specific commercial name: Burnt Oil Shale (Eesti Energia, 2017). Burnt Oil Shale is primarily used in industrial installations for the production of cements and other hydraulic binders. It is also used in soil stabilization and as a fertilizer in agriculture.

9.5 **Waste ash from energy production in Russia**

There are about 350 power plants and coal-fired combined heat and power plants in Russia. About 145 of them are large plants with volume of ash formation more than 100,000 tonnes per year for each. At the same time about 100 of them are positioning themselves as potential suppliers of ash. Annual output of ashes and slag is about 22 mln tonnes. Less than 4 mln tonnes of pulverized fuel ash is delivered to consumers' market. According to the different estimates, from 1.5 to 1.8 bln tonnes of ash and slag materials are accumulated on ash-disposal sites. Capacity of ash-disposal sites of 110 Russian power plants is nearly exhausted. Such situation reveals local environmental disasters and inefficient work with these problems in Russia. For historical reasons, the power industry of the country was focused only on cheap energy production. Problems of production waste treatment were relegated to the side lines, and often were forgotten. Moreover, this was expressed in design choices. Thus, for example, Reftinskaya power plant producing 5-6 mln tonnes of ash per year until very recently had only two silo pits with capacity of 2500 tonnes each. And these are the largest silo pits of all the coal-fired power plants in Russia. Most power plants have no silo pits for ash delivery to consumers at all, and, consequently, no ash treatment systems, designed for its commercialization (Fenix Consortium, 2015).

There are no strong incentives that would force power engineers to deal with the problems of ash commercialization. In European countries ash-disposal areas of coal-fired power plants are either prohibited, or are subject to fine, the amount of which is €90 in Italy to €120 Euro in Germany for each tonne of ash sent to the ash-disposal area. In Russia this fee makes up the sum of 15-20 rubles per tonne (0.2 Euro) maximum. Federal Law No. 219 came into effect in January 2015 according to which since 2020 eco-payments will grow 25–100 times. In addition to this, it is possible to include the costs associated with ash disposal into the cost of energy.

Regulatory framework of the Russian Federation on the use of fly ash of thermal power plants the Russian standard GOST 25818-91 "CHP plants' fly ashes for concretes was updated recently into GOST 25818-2017" CHP plants' fly ashes for concretes. Technical Conditions".

9.6 CO₂ mineral carbonation using concrete demolition waste

Concrete demolition generates considerable amounts of waste. Residual alkalinity of concrete demolition waste (CDW) could make it possible to use it for CO₂ mineral carbonation a potential future option for CO₂ sequestration for those EU member states which do not have sufficient geological storage capacity. Considering low binding ability of CDW samples collected in Italia and studied during CLEANKER project in laboratory (task 7.5), only Italian and Estonian regulations for CDW are discussed in this report.

9.6.1 Italian case

1. *EU Waste Directive, Waste Act*

The definition of waste is specified in the Italian law in the article 183 of D.lgs. n.152/06 (Decreto Legislativo, 2006), where "waste" is defined in compliance with the definition of the Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC (WFD) (EC, 2008).

Concrete demolition waste is part of the construction and demolition waste (CDW Italy, 2015).

No legal text exists with a specific definition of CDW in Italy. CDW are considered in general as waste from construction and demolition activities. They include all waste codes from European List of Waste, 2000/532/EC code 17 (EC, 2008).

2. *Waste management plans (WMP) and Strategies*

Italy has not developed a national waste management plan, as the legislation provides that plans are developed at regional level. However, general criteria for the implementation of regional plans are defined in article 199 of legislative decree 152/2006 (Legislative Decree, 2006).

Regional legislation is very broad and refers to several types of waste. Almost all Regions have also set specific provisions for CDW. However, a detailed analysis of the different

kind of programmes related to CDW, which have been approved in the 20 Italian regions, has not been possible so far (CDW Italy, 2015).

3. *Definitions of waste treatment operations*

Italian definitions for waste treatment operations are in line with the Annex II of the WFD. In Italy the definition of recovery contained in the EU directive 2008/98/EC, is implemented by the legislative decree. n. 205/2010.

9.6.2 Estonian Case

1. EU Waste Directive, Waste Act

The EU Waste Framework Directive (WFD) (2008/98/EC) has been transposed into Estonian legislation through the Waste Act (RT I 2004, 9, 52), adopted in 2004, and its subsequent amendments (the most recent one in 2018) as well as subordinated regulations. Concrete demolition waste is part of the construction and demolition waste (CDW) (EC, 2008, Riigikogu, 2018, CDW Estonia, 2015). The Waste Act does not include specific rules for CDW management but lays down the general rules that should apply for the management of waste according to the waste hierarchy, as presented in the WFD (2008/98/EC). (2008/98/EC). This means that each professional activity related to CDW management falls under appropriate permitting regulations as described in Chapter 6 of the Waste Act concerning Waste Permits. All companies entitled to such Waste Permits are obliged to deliver yearly waste reports to the Environmental Board.

2. National Waste Management Plan 2014-2020

Estonia has a National Waste Management Plan (WMP) for the period 2014-2020 (Keskkonnaministeerium, 2014). A chapter of the new WMP is dedicated to the development of the national Waste Prevention Plan (WPP), according to provisions stated in the WFD (2008/98/EC). The WMP places specific focus on the promotion and intensification of support for investments and financing to companies engaged in waste recycling in order to enhance their performance and treatment capacity with the aim of contributing to the achievement of both recovery/recycling targets of the WFD. The goal of Estonia, as described in the WMP, is to reduce land-filling as much as possible and recover the highest possible share of wastes. CDW is considered as a priority waste stream in the WPP section within the WMP of Estonia.

3. The Environmental Charges Act

The Environmental Charges Act (RT I 2005, 67, 512) describes the conditions under which the landfill operators should pay landfill tax to the State for receiving waste in landfills. There is also the option to issue more detailed rules concerning CDW, based on the Waste Act paragraph 29 (Riigikogu, 2017b.)

There is no specific legislation in place for the management of CDW, but the management of CDW is well articulated in the local waste management rules which are issued at municipality level. CDW therefore, is regulated at municipality level with the obligatory rules laid down in the local government waste management rules (Waste Act, Art.71). The local waste management rules are governed by the provisions of the National Waste Management Plan as well as the Regional Waste Management Plans.

10. SUMMARY FOR COUNTRIES

10.1 Italy

Paris Climate Agreement

Italy has ratified the Paris Climate Agreement on 11 Nov 2016 (Table 2.1).

CO₂ emissions

Its total fossil CO₂ emissions decreased from 423.3 Mt in 1990 to 358.1 Mt in 2016. CO₂ emissions per capita Italy was 6.03 tonnes (Table 2.2).

Climate and energy strategic targets

Italia did not yet defined its national 2050 strategic targets (Table 2.4), but according to Italian National Energy Strategy 2017, Italy defined its 2030 targets as: reducing final energy consumption by a total of 10 Mtoe, reaching a 28% share of renewables in total energy consumption and a 55% share of renewables in electricity consumption. By 2025 Italy is planning to phasing out the use of coal in electricity generation.

London Protocol

Italy has ratified the London Protocol, but did not ratified yet 2009 amendment to article 6, enabling the export of carbon dioxide streams for the purpose of sequestration in trans-boundary sub-seabed geological formations (Figure 3.1, Table 3.1).

OSPAR Convention

Italy is a party of the OSPAR Convention under the European Union sign (Table 3.1).

EU CCS Directive

Italy passed a new legislation to regulate the geological storage of carbon. Legislative Decree No 162 of 14 September 2011 entered into force on 5 October 2011. CO₂ storage is permitted in Italy except for the seismic areas (Table 4.2). Italy is completing a Strategic Environmental Assessment that will allow assessing the available storage capacity. Among studied countries an application for a storage permit was under evaluation only in Italy (EC, 2017).

Prospects for CO₂ storage

Italy has very good geological options for CO₂ storage of Italian CO₂ emissions. The main regulations for CO₂ storage have been developed in Italy. Additional regulations should be taken for clarification of some specific CCS regulatory issues, especially for transboundary storage. 2009 amendment to article 6 of London Protocol, enabling the export of carbon

dioxide streams for the purpose of sequestration in trans-boundary sub-seabed geological formations should be ratified.

CO₂ storage capacity

In EU GeoCapacity project CO₂ storage capacity in deep saline aquifers was estimated as 4669 Mt and in hydrocarbon fields as 1810 Mt (Table 4.3).

Monitoring requirements of the storage sites in Italian regulations mostly corresponds to EU CCS Directive (Table 4.4). Italian CCS Decree includes Annex I (analogue to Annex I to CCS directive about characterisation and assessment of the potential storage complex) and Annex II (criteria for establishing and updating the plan) analogue to the Annex II to CCS directive.

Transboundary issues

Italian CCS Decree in Article 28 obliges operators of CO₂ transport networks and storage sites to guarantee the connection and free access to its transportation network and storage sites to other operators in the transparent and non-discriminatory manner. However, it is also stated that “transport network operators and operators of storage sites may refuse access for lack of ability or link”. Transnational cooperation is regulated only in short by Article 30 of Italian CCS Decree: “For cross-border transport of CO₂ storage sites or transboundary storage complexes, the Ministry of economic development and the Ministry of environment shall fulfil the provisions of this Decree and other applicable Community standards, or promote the conclusion of agreements with countries outside the European Union”.

Global CCS Institute Assessment (2015)

Italy was assigned into Band B with score 56.5 (CCS-specific laws or existing laws that are applicable across parts of the CCS project cycle) (Table 6.1).

EU ETS

Operates in Italy, as EU Member State. In 2015 Italy registered in EU ETS 1071 installations, which produced 143635 Kt CO₂. Among them 93 installations produced >0.5 mln t CO₂ (Table 7.1). CO₂ Emissions from industrial installations as a percentage of the previous year (EU ETS) were more or less stable during 2013-2017, varying from 92.8% in 2014 to 100.2 in 2017.

CO₂ Use for Enhanced Oil Recovery (CO₂-EOR)

Italy has significant capacity for CO₂ storage in hydrocarbon fields (Table 4.3). It means that CO₂ use for EOR and CO₂ storage in the depleted oil fields is a prospective option for Italy. For this case Italian CCS law for CO₂ storage and monitoring and could be applied. Emissions sources at the injection site and from enhanced hydrocarbon recovery can be monitored using existing approaches from the Monitoring and Reporting Guidelines under the ETS Directive (Commission Decision 2007/589/EC and its amendment Commission Decision 2010/345/EU). Combustion emissions at injection site can be monitored with approaches from Annex II (stationary combustion), vented emissions at injection and at enhanced hydrocarbon recovery with approaches from Annex XII (continuous emission measurement) and fugitive emissions at injection by industry best practice.

Prospects for CO₂ use

CO₂ use for EOR is considered by authors of this report as very prospective and beneficiary for Italy.

Renewable Energy (RE)

Italy has already reached its RE 2020 target (17%) in 2014. Its 2030 RE target is 28% and 55% of RE from total energy. Its 2030 target for electricity heating is not available (Table 9.2).

CO₂ Use for Geothermal Energy Recovery (CO₂ - GER)

CO₂ has not been used yet in Italy for GER, but Italy is one of the world's leading countries in terms of geothermal resources. Geothermal resources are mainly utilised for electricity production, and all plants are located in the region of Tuscany, specifically Larderello-Travale and Mount Amiata. In 2013, Enel Green Power installed the first binary power plant in Italy, Gruppo Binario Bangore 3 of 1 MW. In 2015, Cornia 2 power plant has been upgraded with the integration of biomass fired boiler (using local forest biomass) to raise geothermal steam temperatures from about 150°C to 380°C. This hybridisation added 5 MW of capacity to the plant and output is expected to increase by 30 GW per year (WEC, 2018). Installed capacity and production for geothermal electricity and district heating in 2016 is the highest in Italy among the studied countries (Table 9.3).

Prospects for CO₂ use

CO₂ use for GER is considered by authors of this report as very prospective and beneficiary for Italy. In case of GER will be implemented, regulations for Renewable Energy and existing approaches from the Monitoring and Reporting Guidelines under the ETS Directive (Commission Decision 2007/589/EC and its amendment Commission Decision 2010/345/EU) could be applied as described in this document for EOR.

Hazardous wastes

Italy generated in 2014 considerable amount of hazardous waste in three categories W012, W121 and W 124 with correspondingly 6, 3 and 9 kg per capita (Table 9.4).

CDW are considered in general as waste from construction and demolition activities. They include all waste codes from European List of Waste, 2000/532/EC code 17. Italy has not developed a national waste management plan, as the legislation provides that plans are developed at regional level. However, general criteria for the implementation of regional plans are defined in article 199 of legislative decree 152/2006. Regional legislation is very broad and refers to several types of waste. Almost all Regions have also set specific provisions for CDW.

Prospects for CO₂ use

Concrete demolition waste samples from cement industry from Italy studied in WP7 in laboratory did not show high CO₂ binding properties. It could be possible that other waste categories in Italy have better CO₂ mineralisation properties, however they were not studied in this project.

10.2 Estonia

Paris Climate Agreement

Estonia has ratified the Paris Climate Agreement on 4 Nov 2016 (Table 2.1).

CO₂ emissions

Its total fossil CO₂ emissions decreased from 36.97 Mt in 1990 to 22.4 Mt in 2016. CO₂ emissions per capita Estonia was 17.1 tonnes in 2016, being 2.5 times higher than in EU28 and 3.5 times higher than in the world (Table 2.2).

Climate and energy strategic targets

By 2050, Estonia is aiming to decrease greenhouse gas emissions (GHGE) by nearly 80% compared to the level of 1990. To reach these targets, by 2030 about 70% of GHGE and by 2040 about 72% of GHGE should be reduced (Table 2.4). If the policies are implemented, then by 2050, GHGE will have decreased the most in the energy sector and industry (by 67%) (Keskkonnaministeerium 2017).

London Protocol

Estonia has ratified the London Protocol, but did not ratify yet 2009 amendment to article 6, enabling the export of carbon dioxide streams for the purpose of sequestration in trans-boundary sub-seabed geological formations (Figure 3.1, Table 3.1).

OSPAR Convention

Estonia is a party of the OSPAR Convention under the European Union sign (Table 3.1).

Helsinki Convention (HELCOM)

Estonia is a contracting party to HELCOM (Table 3.1).

EU CCS Directive

Estonia has banned CCS in its territories (both onshore and offshore) (Table 4.2) and therefore, the transposition of the CCS Directive was focused primarily on CO₂ transport networks. The exploration and storage permits for CCS are not allowed in Estonia. The Ministry of Environment of Estonia is the only competent authority responsible for fulfilling duties established under Article 23 of the Directive, except in the case of construction of a transboundary transport pipeline, which requires a permit from the Government.

The territory of Estonia, the exclusive economic zone and continental shelf of Estonia are unsuitable for CO₂ storage within the meaning of UNCLOS and Directive 2009/31/EU. Therefore, the Earth's Crust Act and the draft Act amending the Water Act, prohibit the geological storage of CO₂ in both the earth's crust or in sea areas. Exploration permits stipulated in Article 5 of the Directive 2009/31/EC are not used in Estonia. Although there are no specific CO₂ storage capacity studies ordered by the legal authority, published studies of Estonian researchers indicate that CO₂ storage is very unfavourable for onshore storage (Shogenova et al, 2009a, b, 2011).

CO₂ storage capacity

Estonia has not CO₂ storage capacity that is explained by its shallow sedimentary basin and potable water in all the available aquifers (Table 4.3, Shogenova et al, 2009a, b, 2011).

Monitoring

Commission Decision 2010/345/EU amending Commission Decision 2007/589/EC is a basis for regulation determining the emissions from CO₂ storage and transport in Estonia, including provisions for reporting. Operators must submit an annual report to the Ministry of Environment of Estonia on the monitoring technology used and the quantities of CO₂ transported for storage during the reporting period. Operators must keep a record of the quantities and chemical content of the CO₂ transported, which should be sent to the Ministry of Environment once a year. Article 15 (including routine and non-routine inspections) is not applied in Estonia as there are no storage complexes or storage sites suitable for storing carbon dioxide as required by directive 2009/31/EC (Table 4.4).

Transport networks and transboundary issues

According to the Water Act the permit is required for the construction of CO₂ transport pipelines underwater and this permit is issued by the Minister of Environment. Also, the requirement for submerging a cable line under water and consent for this is granted by the Government.

According to Planning Act the CO₂ transport pipeline that runs underground through several local government areas is considered to be a linear structure, the corridor of which is established under country plans.

According to the Act Amending the Ambient Air Protection Act (RT I 31.12.2010, 31) 'the owner or operator of the existing transport pipeline has an obligation to connect to the existing CO₂ transport pipeline by pipeline of another entity who has requested that ('accessing entity') if the technical conditions allow for it and it does not pose a risk to the existing transport capacity, people's health or environment'. Any refusals must be explained in writing within 30 days of receiving the access application.

Global CCS Institute Assessment (2015)

Estonia was assigned into Band C with score 31 (very few CCS-specific or existing laws that are applicable across parts of the CCS project cycle) (Table 6.1).

Prospects for CO₂ storage

Estonia has no geological options for CO₂ storage in Estonia, but possibilities to store captured in Estonia CO₂ in Latvian onshore and offshore structures should be considered. To implement offshore storage, 2009 amendment to article 6 of London Protocol, enabling the export of carbon dioxide streams for the purpose of sequestration in trans-boundary sub-seabed geological formations should be ratified by Estonia and all participating in the project countries should be members of the London Protocol.

EU ETS

Operates in Estonia, as EU Member State. In 2015 Estonia registered 45 installations, which produced 10996 Kt CO₂. Among them four installations produced >0.5 mln t CO₂ and eight installations produced in the range 0.05-0.5 mln t CO₂ (Table 7.1). CO₂ Emissions from industrial installations as a percentage of the previous year (EU ETS) increased in 2016 (112.49%) and in 2017 (109.22%). National installations registered in 2015 in EU ETS

produced 10996 kt of CO₂ in Estonia, (Table 7.1). During 2015-2017 registered in EU ETS emissions significantly increased in Estonia (about 20% during 2016-2017).

According to the EU ETS, AS Kunda Nordic Tsement Plant produced 0.56 Mt/CO₂ in 2017. It is the main and only one cement producer in Estonia and one of the eight largest Estonian CO₂ emission sources, which produced together 14 Mt CO₂ in 2017 (Simmer, 2018).

CO₂ Use for Enhanced Oil Recovery (CO₂-EOR)

Estonia does not have hydrocarbon deposits (Table 4.3). Estonian local oil shale kukersite is used for energy production, for ex-situ production of oil, cement production and is used in the chemical industry.

Prospects for CO₂ use

There is no prospect for CO₂ use for EOR in Estonia, but Estonian CO₂ could be transported to Latvia, Lithuania and Kaliningrad Region of Russia for CO₂-EOR and CO₂ storage.

Renewable Energy (RE)

Estonia has already reached its 2020 renewable energy target.

CO₂ Use for Geothermal Energy Recovery (CO₂-GER)

CO₂ has not been used yet in Estonia for GER. Geothermal energy does not play any big role as a RES, as the geothermal conditions are not favourable and the geothermal gradient is lower than the average level. No thermal waters are found in Estonia (USDA, 2016).

Only shallow geothermal energy is used for heating in Estonia. Total production of energy is only 2 times lower than in Lithuania, but more than 10 times higher than in Latvia.

Installed capacity and production for geothermal electricity and district heating in 2016 is at the second place among the studied three Baltic States (Table 9.3).

Prospects for CO₂ use

Prospects for CO₂ use for GER in Estonia should be estimated after economic modelling study will be made for CO₂ use for the deep geothermal energy which could be of low enthalpy (about 40°C at the depth of one km).

Hazardous wastes

The EU Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC) has been transposed into Estonian legislation through the Waste Act (RT I 2004, 9, 52), adopted in 2004, and its subsequent amendments (the most recent one in 2018) as well as subordinated regulations

Burning 1 t of Estonian oil shale gives approximately 0.45 t of hazardous alkaline ash (contains up to 50% CaO and 15% MgO) waste. Ash alkalinity makes it possible to use it for CO₂ mineral carbonation – a potential future option for CO₂ sequestration.

Estonia produces around 8.6 mln tonnes of hazardous combustion waste per year (mainly oil shale ash), corresponding to 6600 tonnes of hazardous waste per capita. These numbers of the produced total combustion wastes are 15 times higher than in Italy, and 700 times higher than per capita in Italy (Table 9.4).

According to regulation of Minister of the Environment (RT I, 18.12.2015, 14), oil shale bottom ash and oil shale flow ash are listed as hazardous waste with codes 10 01 97* and 10 01 98* respectively.

The Waste Act does not include specific rules for oil shale ash waste management, but lays down the general rules that should apply for the management of waste according to the waste hierarchy, as presented in the WFD (2008/98/EC).

Estonia has a National Waste Management Plan (WMP) for the period 2014-2020. The goal of Estonia, as described in the WMP, is to reduce land-filling as much as possible and recover the highest possible share of wastes. Oil shale ash is considered as a priority waste stream in the WMP of Estonia.

To simplify the re-usage of oil shale ash, Eesti Energia has created a Material Safety Data Sheet for Oil Shale Thermal Processing Residue with the following specific commercial name: Burnt Oil Shale. Burnt Oil Shale is primarily used in industrial installations for the production of cements and other hydraulic binders. It is also used in soil stabilization and as a fertilizer in agriculture.

Prospects for CO₂ use

Estonian oil shale ash has high CO₂ binding properties and has very good prospects to be used in CO₂ mineral carbonation process (Uibu et al, 2010).

10.3 Latvia

Paris Climate Agreement

Latvia has ratified the Paris Climate Agreement on 16 Mar 2017 (Table 2.1).

CO₂ emissions

Its total fossil CO₂ emissions decreased from 20.32 Mt in 1990 to 8.16 Mt in 2016. CO₂ emissions per capita in Latvia was only 4.14 tonnes (Table 2.2), that is lower than average in the world and Europe.

Climate and energy strategic targets

Latvia did not yet defined its 2050 strategic targets, but according to EU Decision 529/2013 country has to decrease its emissions to 40% by 2030 and to 80% by 2050 compared to base year 1990 (Table 2.4).

London Protocol

Latvia is not a party of London Conventions and London Protocol (Figure 3.1)

OSPAR Convention

Latvia is a party of the OSPAR Convention under the European Union sign (Table 3.1).

Helsinki Convention, 1992 (HELCOM)

Latvia is a contracting party to HELCOM (Table 3.1).

EU CCS Directive

Latvia has made amendments to national legislation to transpose the Directive. A framework has been established for obtaining permits for capture installations to carry out polluting activities, requirements have been set to regulate CO₂ transportation and a purity criterion has been established. The Saeima (Latvian Parliament) has adopted legislative amendments prohibiting the storage of CO₂ within Latvia's borders, its exclusive economic zone, and on its continental shelf. The duration of the ban is dependent on information to be

provided by the Ministry of Environmental Protection and Regional Development to the Parliament. The Latvian Parliament will then use this information to determine whether to lift or maintain the ban (Table 4.2).

Latvia explained the ban by: lack of experience in using CCS technology on an industrial scale and dealing with its environmental impact; opposition from experts in the environmental authorities and from environmental organisations; the absence of demand for CCS from Latvia's energy and industrial operators, as natural gas is used as a fuel almost exclusively, and the capacity of combustion plants is small compared to the rest of the EU. Latvia's subterranean structures were intended to be used primarily for natural gas storage and for geothermal energy recovery.

CO₂ storage capacity in deep saline aquifers was estimated as 400 Mt onshore and 300 Mt offshore (Šliaupa et al, 2013), however our studies showed possible larger offshore capacity (Shogenov et al, 2013).

Monitoring requirements of the storage sites in Italian regulations mostly corresponds to EU CCS Directive (Table 4.4). Italian CCS Decree includes Annex I (analogue to Annex I to CCS directive about characterization and assessment of the potential storage complex) and Annex II (criteria for establishing and updating the plan) analogue to the Annex II to CCS directive.

Transboundary issues

Latvia took the law in October 2011 “Arrangements for transporting carbon dioxide flows”, which includes issues on transport networks, pipelines, transboundary transport and CO₂ flow purity (not less than 96% CO₂). The law (consisting of four paragraphs) rules the procedure for the transport of carbon dioxide flows through pipelines to storage areas in geological structures, the purity criteria for carbon dioxide flows and the procedures for the review of access to transport networks and storage areas. The regulation is mainly dedicated to the “third-party access”, and only very shortly regulated transboundary transport, by requirement of cooperation of competent authorities of both bordering Member States.

It is stated that “The transport network operator shall provide a potential user of the transport network with access to the transport network for the transport of carbon dioxide streams through pipelines to areas where carbon dioxide storage is permitted. The operator of the transport network may deny access to the transport network, as a result of lack of capacity or connection”. Also cooperation between Member States is envisaged for the case when the transport network or the storage site is under the jurisdiction of two or more than two Member States.

Latvia has experience in transboundary transport of natural gas (from Russia), and its underground storage and support when necessary to Estonia and Lithuania.

Global CCS Institute Assessment (2015)

Latvia was assigned into Band C with score 31 (very few CCS-specific or existing laws that are applicable across parts of the CCS project cycle) (Table 6.1).

Prospects for CO₂ storage

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 764816. This work is supported by the China Government (National Natural Science Foundation of China) under contract No.91434124 and No.51376105.

Latvia has very good geological options for CO₂ storage of emissions captured in the Baltic Sea Region (BSR) countries without CO₂ storage potential like Estonia and Finland. The largest Latvian emissions could be also stored together.

Regulations for CO₂ storage are not yet enough developed in Latvia and it should be done as soon as possible in order to reach 2030 and 2050 targets in the BSR.

Latvia should join the London Protocol and ratify its 2009 amendment to article 6, enabling the export of carbon dioxide streams for the purpose of sequestration in trans-boundary sub-seabed geological formations should be ratified. Latvia should consider the possible synergy of CO₂ storage and use for Geothermal energy recovery and EOR.

EU ETS

Operates in Latvia, as EU Member State. In 2015 Latvia registered 64 installations, which produced 1714 Kt CO₂. Among them only 2 installations produced >0.5 mln t CO₂ and another 2 produced in the range 0.05-0.5 mln t CO₂ (Table 7.1).

CO₂ Emissions from industrial installations as a percentage of the previous year (EU ETS) are mainly decreasing during last years, varying from 95.8% in 2016 to 94.9 in 2017.

CO₂ Use for Enhanced Oil Recovery (CO₂-EOR)

Latvia has very small hydrocarbon fields onshore and offshore in the western part of the country, and their capacity for CO₂ storage is not estimated. However, possibility for CO₂-EOR and CO₂ storage in the E6 offshore structure was recently proposed (Shogenov et al, 2017, Shogenov and Shogenova, 2017).

Emissions sources at the injection site and from enhanced hydrocarbon recovery can be monitored using existing approaches from the Monitoring and Reporting Guidelines under the ETS Directive (Commission Decision 2007/589/EC and its amendment Commission Decision 2010/345/EU). Combustion emissions at injection site can be monitored with approaches from Annex II (stationary combustion), vented emissions at injection and at enhanced hydrocarbon recovery with approaches from Annex XII (continuous emission measurement) and fugitive emissions at injection by industry best practice.

Prospects for CO₂ use

CO₂ use for EOR is considered by authors of this report as possible useful demonstration of the innovative technology in the Baltic Region (Shogenov et al, 2016, Shogenov and Shogenova, 2017).

Renewable Energy (RE)

Latvia has not yet reached its ambitious RE 2020 target (40%). Its 2030 RE target is 50% Its 2030 target of RE from total energy and for electricity heating is not available.

CO₂ Use for Geothermal Energy Recovery (CO₂-GER)

CO₂ has not been used in Latvia for GER, and Latvian installed capacity and heat production from geothermal energy was very low in 2016 and the lowest among the studied countries (Table 9.3). However, Latvia has geothermal anomalies in the southern part of the western

Latvia, and have prospects for higher use of geothermal energy, supported by discussions by research institutes and industry (Skapare et al, 2015).

Prospects for CO₂ use

CO₂ use for GER is considered by authors of this report as prospective when used in synergy with other innovative technologies and CO₂ storage (Shogenov et al, 2017).

In case of GER will be implemented, regulations for Renewable Energy and existing approaches from the Monitoring and Reporting Guidelines under the ETS Directive (Commission Decision 2007/589/EC and its amendment Commission Decision 2010/345/EU) could be applied as described in this document for EOR.

Hazardous wastes

In 2014 Latvia generated low amount of hazardous waste in three categories W012, W121 and W 124 which are the lowest in the studied countries (Table 9.4).

Prospects for CO₂ use

Considering very low amount of hazardous alkaline waste produced in Latvia, CO₂ use of alkaline waste material has no prospects in Latvia.

10.4 Lithuania

Paris Climate Agreement

Lithuania has ratified the Paris Climate Agreement on 2 February 2017 (Table 2.1).

CO₂ emissions

Its total fossil CO₂ emissions decreased from 35.1 Mt in 1990 to 13.69 Mt in 2016. CO₂ emissions per capita was 4.7 tonnes lower than world and EU28 average numbers (4.8 and 6.75 t, correspondingly) (Table 2.2).

Climate and energy strategic targets

According to information published at the Ministry of Environment homepage the last national strategy for climate change management policy was published in November 2012 aiming to reduce 40/60/80% of GHG emissions by 2030/2040/2050, correspondingly (Table 2.4). CCS is mentioned in this document in the paragraph 89. In the chapter industry, where CCS technology and Lithuanian CCS regulations are described in short. At the end of this paragraph it is stated that “CCS technologies in Lithuania in the near future is quite unlikely due to high cost of technology and absence of storage sites on the territory of the country.” (Ministry of Environment of the Republic of Lithuania, 2012).

London Protocol

Lithuania is not a party of London Conventions and London Protocol (Table 3.1).

OSPAR Convention

Lithuania is a party of the OSPAR Convention under the European Union sign (Table 3.1).

Helsinki Convention, 1992 (HELCOM)

Lithuania is a contracting party to HELCOM (Table 3.1).

EU CCS Directive

Two new legal acts were adopted in Lithuania to regulate the licensing system related to the implementation of the Directive: 1) Law of the Republic of Lithuania on Geological Storage of Carbon Dioxide (Official Gazette, 2011, No 91-4325), referred to as “the Law”. 2) Resolution No 1166 of the Government of the Republic of Lithuania of 5 October 2011 on the approval of the description of the procedure for exploration of carbon dioxide geological complexes, use and closure of carbon dioxide storage sites (Official Gazette, 2011, No 5833-123), referred to as “the Description”. Also in 28 legal acts Lithuania has transposed the specific provisions of the CCS Directive into national law.

Among the Baltic States only Lithuania allowed CO₂ geological storage both onshore and offshore.

Prospects for CO₂ storage

Lithuania has relatively small capacity for onshore CO₂ storage in saline aquifers and depleted oil fields. However the owner of the Latvian and Lithuanian oil fields Minjos Nafta Company made two successful pilot injections in 2013, and estimated the capacity for CO₂ storage in depleted oil fields as 100 mln tonnes (CGS Baltic seed project (S81), 2017), compared to 5.7 mln tonnes estimated earlier (Vangkilde-Pedersen et al, 2009, Sliupa et al, 2013).

CO₂ storage capacity

CO₂ storage capacity in deep saline aquifers was estimated as 29 Mt and in hydrocarbon fields as 5.7 Mt (Sliupa et al, 2013). Capacity in depleted oil fields after CO₂ injections tests made in Lithuania in 2013, where estimated as 100 mln tonnes (CGS Baltic seed project (S81), 2017).

Monitoring requirements of the storage sites in Lithuanian regulations mostly corresponds to EU CCS Directive (Table 4.4). Lithuania is applying the Order No 1-156 of the Deputy Director of the Geological Survey of Lithuania under the Ministry of Environment of 24 August 2011 on the approval of methodological requirements for the preparation of the part of the monitoring program related to ground water monitoring which foresees: ‘51. In order to optimize the monitoring of injection facilities, CO₂ geological storage complex and the surrounding environment, it is advisable to follow the guidance document of the European Commission on the characterization of the storage complex, CO₂ stream composition, monitoring and corrective measures’.

Transboundary issues

Article 19 “*The Republic of Lithuania international cooperation on CO₂ geological storage issues*”, where in only five lines explained: “when the CO₂ transported in more than one Member State of the EU or when the storage or a storage complex is located in more than one Member State of the EU, then Republic of Lithuania together with competent authorities of other EU Member States shall comply with the requirements laid down in the EU legislation on the geological storage of CO₂.”

Article 20 of Lithuanian law “*Access to the pipeline and storage facilities*” is explaining the procedure of giving the access, or refusing the access if there is not enough capacity.

Global CCS Institute Assessment (2015)

Lithuania was assigned into Band B with score 49.5 (CCS-specific laws or existing laws that are applicable across parts of the CCS project cycle) (Table 6.1)

EU ETS operates in Lithuania, as EU Member State. In 2015, Lithuania registered 90 installations, which produced 6028 Kt CO₂. Among them three installations produced >0.5 mln t CO₂ and six installations produced in the range 0.05-0.5 mln t CO₂ (Table 7.1).

CO₂ Use for Enhanced Oil Recovery (CO₂-EOR)

According to Minijos Nafta company CO₂ use for EOR and CO₂ storage in the depleted oil fields is a prospective option for Lithuania. For this case Lithuanian CCS law for CO₂ storage and monitoring and could be applied.

Emissions sources at the injection site and from enhanced hydrocarbon recovery can be monitored using existing approaches from the Monitoring and Reporting Guidelines under the ETS Directive (Commission Decision 2007/589/EC and its amendment Commission Decision 2010/345/EU). Combustion emissions at injection site can be monitored with approaches from Annex II (stationary combustion), vented emissions at injection and at enhanced hydrocarbon recovery with approaches from Annex XII (continuous emission measurement) and fugitive emissions at injection by industry best practice.

Prospects for CO₂ use

CO₂ use for EOR is considered by authors of this report as prospective and beneficiary for Lithuania. Cooperation with Estonia is possible.

Renewable Energy (RE)

Lithuania has already reached its RE 2020 target 23% in 2014. The new goal of Lithuania is to reach a 30 % share of renewable energy sources (RES) in the final energy consumption by 2020. In the next three years, the installed power of wind energy will increase by 50%, and that of solar twice. It is planned that by 2030 RES installed power will be 2.5 times what it is now, and almost half (45%) of the consumed energy should be manufactured from renewable sources; by 2050 energy from renewable and other non-polluting sources will comprise the majority of energy used in the electricity, heating, and transport sectors. By 2050, all electricity should be produced from RES, while in the transportation sector RES energy will amount to 50 % (Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Lithuania, 2018)

CO₂ Use for Geothermal Energy Recovery (CO₂-GER)

CO₂ has not been used yet for GER, but Lithuanian geothermal resource, lying in the west of the country, has been found to be significant. In 2000, the 41 MW Klaipeda Geothermal Demonstration Plant (KGDP) was commissioned and began producing 25% of the heat required by the city of Klaipeda. Much work has been undertaken on the thermal waters in Vilkaviskis, a city in the south-western part of the country, with a view to developing balneological uses and also a district heating scheme. To date, Lithuania's extensive low-temperature resource has been harnessed for an estimated 1000 ground-source heat pumps, with an installed capacity of 17 MW (WEC, 2018). Installed capacity and production for

geothermal electricity and district heating in 2016 is the highest in Lithuania among the studied three Baltic States Table 9.3).

Prospects for CO₂ use

CO₂ use for GER is considered by authors of this report as prospective and beneficiary for Lithuania. Cooperation with Estonia is possible. In case of GER will be implemented, regulations for Renewable Energy and existing approaches from the Monitoring and Reporting Guidelines under the ETS Directive (Commission Decision 2007/589/EC and its amendment Commission Decision 2010/345/EU) could be applied as described in this document for EOR.

Hazardous wastes

Lithuania has generated in 2014 considerable amount of hazardous waste in category W012, with correspondingly 2 kg per capita. In category W121 its waste was insignificant and the lowest among the studied EU countries (Table 9.4).

Prospects for CO₂ use

There is no significant prospect for use of hazardous waste for CO₂ mineral carbonation in Lithuania. However, a large serpentinite province has been discovered in the Palaeoproterozoic crystalline basement of southern Lithuania. Serpentinites associate with the high-quality iron ore, which provides an opportunity for cascade utilization of these formations. Owing to their association with iron ore deposits, these bodies were extensively studied by drilling. Carbon dioxide can be immobilized by reacting with serpentinite to form stable minerals. Roughly, the assumed ratio of immobilized CO₂ to serpentinite is assumed 1:2. The estimated volume of serpentinites of the largest Varena Iron Ore Deposit is 1–2 Gt. Consequently, the sequestration potential is evaluated to be as high as 0.5–1 Gt (Stasiulaitiene et al, 2007, Shogenova et al, 2009). The most sustainable planning for using these serpentinite rocks in Lithuania is first mining of iron ores and then using mining waste for CO₂ mineral carbonation. At the present time there is no national incentives into this direction.

10.5 Russia

Paris Climate Agreement

Russia has signed the Paris Climate Agreement in April 2016, but has not yet ratified it (Table 2.1).

CO₂ emissions

Russia is one of the largest CO₂ emitters in the world its emissions are at the fourth place after China, USA and India (EC JRC, 2018). Its total fossil CO₂ emissions decreased from 2.38 Gt in 1990 to 1.66 Gt in 2016. CO₂ emissions per capita Russia was 11.54 tonnes (Table 2.2).

Climate and energy strategic targets

Russian Federation proposed to reduce emissions 25% to 30% below 1990 levels by 2030 (UNFCCC 2015). According to latest estimates of Climate Action Tracker (CAT 2018),

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Russia's currently implemented policies will lead to emissions of 2.6 GtCO₂e in 2020 and 2.7 GtCO₂e in 2030 (both excluding LULUCF), which is 4% and 11% above 2015 emissions levels, respectively. This represents a decrease in emissions from 1990 levels of 28% in 2020 and 23% in 2030, all below the INDC targets, which allow emissions to grow 8–27% above 2015 levels by 2020 and 18–25% by 2030. According to some expert opinions, Russia can correct and increase 2030 targets to 2.5 GtCO₂e (35-40% from 1990 levels) excluding LULUCF (Bellona, 2018).

London Protocol

Russia has ratified the London Convention, but did not ratify the London Protocol (Figure 3.1, Table 3.1).

OSPAR Convention

Russia is not a party of the OSPAR Convention (Table 3.1).

Helsinki Convention, 1992 (HELCOM)

Russia a contracting party to HELCOM (Table 3.1).

CCS Regulations

Russia does not have specific CCS regulations.

Prospects for CO₂ storage

Russia has very good theoretical geological prospects for CO₂ storage of Russian CO₂ emissions, but locations are too far from the Cesla cement plant in Slantsy town, which was planned to be included in the CCS scenario in the CLEANKER project.

CO₂ storage capacity

Total CO₂ storage capacity of Russia is not yet estimated, however capacity in the Kaliningrad Region for CO₂-EOR is estimated as 33 Mt CO₂ (Table 4.3). Considering very good results of CO₂-EOR tests made in Lithuania in 2013 and increased estimated capacity made afterwards, these numbers could be increased (recalculated), as geological conditions of Kaliningrad oil fields should be close to Lithuanian fields.

Monitoring requirements of the storage sites are not available in Russia.

Transboundary issues

Russia does not have any laws regulating CO₂ transport in Russia or cross-border CO₂ transport. However, Russia is transporting natural gas by pipelines into many countries. This is regulated by available Russian Federation international agreements with the countries where it is transported and international Marine Agreements (United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, UNCLOS) in case of offshore transport (Langlet, 2014).

Global CCS Institute Assessment (2015)

Russia was assigned into Band C with score 33 (very few CCS-specific or existing laws that are applicable across parts of the CCS project cycle) (Table 6.1).

EU ETS

Not applicable for Russia. CO₂ tax is not applied in Russia.

CO₂ Use for Enhanced Oil Recovery (CO₂ -EOR)

Russia has significant capacity for CO₂ storage in depleted hydrocarbon fields, which is not yet fully estimated. Recently RITEC company (LUKOIL Group) for the first time in Russia has injected 300 tonnes CO₂ into the oil deposit with high viscosity oil properties into the Marjino Deposit (Samara Region). Injection of CO₂ decreased viscosity of the oil for 10 times. Initial debit of the well was 8.6 tonnes per days. At the present time ongoing monitoring works will determine the optimal regime, oil recovery parameters and oil viscosity dynamics (OilGasCom, 2018).

Renewable Energy (RE)

Share of energy from renewable sources (in % of gross final energy consumption) in 2015 has been only 3.3% in Russia (Table 9.2), but Russia has very large RE resources.

CO₂ Use for Geothermal Energy Recovery (CO₂-GER)

Russia has significant geothermal resources especially in such regions as Kamchatka. Installed capacity and production for geothermal electricity and district heating in 2016 is higher in Russia than in the studied Baltic Countries (Table 9.3).

Prospects for CO₂ use

CO₂ use for GER is considered by authors of this report as very prospective and beneficiary for Russia, but research regulations and political incentives are needed.

Hazardous wastes

Russian power industry produces 30.4 mln tonnes of ash & slag materials yearly. Only 4 mln tonnes of ash materials is used for various purposes, everything else is sent to ash disposal sites (Fenix Consortium, 2015).

Prospects for CO₂ use

Russia has very good prospect for mineral carbonation of coal ashes. In the Leningrad Region only 2.5 mln tonnes of oil shale is produced, which is mainly used for chemical industry and metallurgy. There are prospects for using coal ash for mineral carbonation process as one of the additional way for possible already applied ash uses (cement production, road construction, agriculture, etc.).

11. GAPS IN AVAILABLE REGULATIONS AND CLIMATE STRATEGIES

The following gaps in implementation of the available regulations and national climate strategies are reported in these chapter.

11.1 International Regulations

For the implementation of the Italian and Baltic CCS scenarios, planned in the CLEANKER project, the main gaps in the international regulations are the following:

- 1) Russia did not ratify yet climate agreement
- 2) Latvia, Lithuania and Russia are not yet parties of the London Protocol.

All the studied five countries (parties of the London Protocol – Italy and Estonia) and not parties (Latvia, Lithuania and Russia) have to ratify 2009 amendment to the article 6 of the London protocol, enabling the export of carbon dioxide streams for the purpose of sequestration in trans-boundary sub-seabed geological formations (Figure 3.1, Table 3.1). Latvia, Lithuania and Russia can do it only after joining the London Protocol.

11.2 CCS Directive and strategic planning

Among studied five countries, the most developed CCS regulations are available in Italy and Lithuania (band B according to GCCSI evaluation, Table 2.1).

CO₂ storage is permitted except for the seismic areas in Italy, and CCS Directive is mostly implemented for all aspects. However, some specific questions and issues should be developed additionally (for example transboundary and some monitoring issues, etc.).

The most important gap for these two countries that CCUS is not yet included in the Italian and Lithuanian strategic energy and climate plans. There is still some probability that these plans will be adjusted by 2019 or later to include CCUS.

Estonia, Latvia and Russia are in the band C according to GCCSI evaluation (Table 2.1). CO₂ storage is not permitted in these countries, but reasons for this and situation in all countries are different.

Latvia has very good/safe structures for CO₂ storage and 50 years of experience of Inčukalna UGS at their territory. At the moment the CO₂ storage is banned in Latvia. However, the law for transboundary transport of CO₂ is implemented. Latvia wanted to give priority for its geological structures to natural gas and geothermal energy uses. But considering Latvian policy of last years, the new UGS most probably will be not developed, in order not to increase energy dependence from Russia. Deep geothermal energy projects are also not developing in practice in Latvia now. It looks that there is no conflict of interest with other uses. Also geothermal energy could be used in synergy with CO₂ storage at the same storage sites (Shogenov et al, 2017). It means that Latvia can rise the ban in case if CCUS projects and technologies will be demonstrated at least in some EU countries. By that time research pilot CCUS project should developed to demonstrate possibilities and advantages of the technology.

Estonia has banned CO₂ storage by another reasons. Country has shallow sedimentary basin and potable water in all aquifers, therefore its storage potential is estimated as zero (Shogenova et al, 2009).

However, in June 2018 Estonian Research Council has opened the call for applied research, as a support for strategic R&D activities, titled “Possibilities for climate change mitigation by industrial carbon dioxide capture and utilization“ to estimate options for CO₂ capture and use in Estonia and possible transport and export of CO₂ for use and storage. The results of this study will be available at the beginning of 2021. Regulatory and economic aspect as well as needed additional regulations and political incentives should be also covered in the

report. After this research is ready Estonian government will take decision about possible further planning and political support of CCUS in Estonia.

Russia has no any specific regulations for CCUS technology, and there is no any strategic plans to implement it. However, one very important driver which can move situation forward is commercial interest of the oil and gas national and private companies to use CO₂ for EOR. The first and successful test for CO₂ injection into the oil field in Russia has been done in 2018 in Samara region (OilGasCom, 2018). The research projects to estimate CO₂-EOR prospects are also ordered in Russia. It is not any signals yet that this interest will grow some-when into large industrial CO₂-EOR and CO₂ storage projects. Very low strategical climate targets of Russia don't need to apply CCUS technology and even not enough ambitious to implement all potential of renewable energies in Russia. Now Russian government relies on the largest in the world forest areas in Russia, which they think will permit them to meet their presented to UNFCCC climate targets (UNFCCC, 2015).

11.3 CO₂ USE

11.3.1 CO₂ use for enhanced recovery of resources

Among studied countries Italy and Russia has the best geological conditions for CO₂ use for EOR and GER. Among three Baltic States Lithuania has the best geological conditions for these technologies. Latvia has some, but mostly limited possibilities because of the very small oil deposits and lower underground temperatures than in other studied countries.

Estonia does not have any prospects for CO₂-EOR, because of the absent oil deposits. The underground temperatures are also the lowest. We can propose to use CO₂ instead of water or together with water for recovery of geothermal energy using pumping and other technologies. Because CO₂ is much more effective coming back to the surface the part of the pumping energy could be saved if water is used together with CO₂ dissolved. However, these technology is not yet demonstrated, it could be too expensive for small users and techno-economic studies should be made to estimate its relevance and applicability in the country.

In EU countries there are EU regulations for monitoring of CO₂ emissions at the storage site used for EHR. Emissions sources at the injection site and from enhanced hydrocarbon recovery can be monitored using existing approaches from the Monitoring and Reporting Guidelines under the ETS Directive (Commission Decision 2007/589/EC and its amendment Commission Decision 2010/345/EU). Combustion emissions at injection site can be monitored with approaches from Annex II (stationary combustion), vented emissions at injection and at enhanced hydrocarbon recovery with approaches from Annex XII (continuous emission measurement) and fugitive emissions at injection by industry best practice. CO₂ use for Enhanced Geothermal Recovery is not mentioned in these laws and it is the main gap in the regulations for this technology now.

11.3.2 CO₂ mineral carbonation using wastes

According to regulation of Minister of the Environment of Estonia, oil shale bottom ash and oil shale flow ash are listed as hazardous wastes with codes 10 01 97* and 10 01 98*, respectively. The Waste Act does not include specific rules for oil shale ash waste management, but lays down the general rules that should apply for the management of waste according to the waste hierarchy, as presented in the WFD (2008/98/EC).

Estonia has a National Waste Management Plan (WMP) for the period 2014-2020. The goal of Estonia is to reduce land-filling as much as possible and recover the highest possible share of wastes. Oil shale ash is considered as a priority waste stream in the WMP of Estonia (Keskkonnaministeerium, 2014).

To simplify the re-usage of oil shale ash, Eesti Energia has created a Material Safety Data Sheet for Oil Shale Thermal Processing Residue with the following specific commercial name: Burnt Oil Shale (Eesti Energia, 2017). Burnt Oil Shale is primarily used in industrial installations for the production of cements and other hydraulic binders. It is also used in soil stabilization and as a fertilizer in agriculture.

The main gap is a need to make amendment in the Estonian regulations via moving of Estonian oil shale ash from the category of “hazardous wastes” into category of commercial products with the name Burnt Oil Shale (Eesti Energia, 2017).

Regulations for CDW is not discussed in this chapter, as the studied Italian samples were found not prospective for CO₂ binding.

Other waste materials should be studied and discussed for Italy, Latvia and Lithuania. In Lithuania the prospective waste material for CO₂ mineral carbonation could appear after possible exploitation of iron ores in the available serpentinite deposits (Shogenova et al, 2009).

Russia has a lot of coal ashes and slags produced. Its binding abilities for CO₂ mineral carbonation should be studied in the laboratory in the next projects. Research and developing works, regulations and political incentives for CO₂ use activities with waste materials are needed.

12. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR REGULATIONS UPDATES, POLITICAL INCENTIVES AND OTHER NEEDED ACTIONS

12.1 Italian Scenario

Italy has good options for CO₂ use and storage in Lombardy Region. Recently ENI has run various studies and preliminary evaluations as part of the design of surface infrastructure for CO₂ injection and monitoring in the Cortemaggiore field (Piacenza). ENI has also analysed the legal and societal aspects linked to storage here. The injection of 8000 tonnes of CO₂ per year was planned over a three-year period, followed by two years of post injection monitoring. Studies on the utilization of the CO₂ were also planned in order to

increase the recovery factor from Italian hydrocarbon fields (Rütters et al, 2013). However, these plans were not yet realised and results of feasibility study made by ENI is confidential and not available to public. Italy is one of the world's leading countries in terms of geothermal resources which are mainly utilised for electricity production.

Considering these issues, CO₂ captured at the Piacenza Cement plant could be stored using local CO₂ storage and use options. For implementing of the Italian local onshore scenario the following actions are needed:

- 1) Inclusion of CCUS technology into Italian strategic climate and energy plans together with renewable energy.
- 2) Research and feasibility study which will demonstrate possibility of synergy of CO₂-EOR, CO₂ storage and CO₂ use for geothermal energy recovery at the same storage site.
- 3) Political decisions to start full chain CCUS projects in Italy, accompanied with additional regulations based on available four guidance documents to CCS Directive and Emission Monitoring Guidance.
- 4) Support of local authorities in the exploration and storage permits procedures.
- 5) Both national and industrial and EU support to start the first full CCUS project in Italy
- 6) Educational and increasing public awareness activities supported by academic and research institutions and media support to explain benefits of climate change mitigation.
- 7) For utilization of offshore storage capacity in Italy Ratification of 2009 amendment to article 6 to London Protocol by two third of the London Protocol parties.

12.2 Baltic Scenario

Baltic CCUS scenario can potentially involve emissions, storage and utilization options of four countries – Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania and western Russia. Russia is one of the largest emitters in the world, Estonia has the highest CO₂ emissions per capita in Europe (second after Luxemburg). Latvia has the best storage options close to the Kunda cement plant (planned for scenario in the CLEANKER). Lithuania and Russia have already tested CO₂ injections in the oil fields (2013 and 2018 correspondingly) and got very promising results. Latvia and Russia have 50 years of experience of underground natural gas storages (Incukalns in Latvia and Gatchina in Leningrad Region) where storage is located in the prospective in the Baltic Region storage reservoir. Estonia has made laboratory experimental tests for mineral carbonation of CO₂ with oil shale ash, demonstrated high binding properties.

Two possible Estonian – Latvian scenarios are proposed in the Master thesis defended in June 2018 in Tallinn University of Technology (Simmer, 2018).

For developing and realization of Baltic CCUS scenarios the following actions are needed:

- 1) Ratification of Paris agreement by Russia and joining of the London Protocol by Latvia, Lithuania and Russia.

- 2) Ratification of 2009 amendment to article 6 to London Protocol by two third of the London Protocol parties.
- 3) EU Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region (BSR) is an example of research and developing cooperation options possible among studied four countries. The BSR strategy should include CCUS as one of the priority area.
- 4) Inclusion of CCUS technology into Estonian, Latvian, Lithuanian and Russian strategic climate and energy plans together with renewable energy.
- 5) Rising ban to CCS storage in Latvia and implementation of CCUS regulations and CO₂ emission monitoring regulations in Russia.
- 6) International and economic relations of EU with Russia should be improved by lifting of economic and political sanctions and mitigation of military reinforcement.
- 7) EU Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region is an example of research and developing cooperation options possible among studied four countries. The BSR strategy should include CCUS as one of the priority area.
- 8) Research and feasibility study which will demonstrate possibility of synergy of CO₂-EOR, CO₂ storage and CO₂ use for geothermal energy recovery at the same storage site (possible in Latvia, Lithuania and Kaliningrad Region of Russia).
- 9) Political decisions to start full chain CCUS projects in Latvia and Lithuania and Russia accompanied with additional regulations based on available four guidance documents to CCS Directive and Emission Monitoring Guidance. In Latvia all issues connected to storage site, monitoring and transferring of responsibility should be implemented. In Russia all needed for CCUs chain laws are needed. In Estonia political decisions to start CO₂ capture, use and export projects are needed.
- 10) Support of local authorities in the exploration and storage permits procedures in the storage site countries.
- 11) Both national, industrial and EU support are needed to start the first full CCUS project in the Baltic States and Russia.
- 12) Educational and increasing public awareness activities supported by academic and research institutions and media support to explain benefits of climate change mitigation.

13. CONCLUSIONS

- International and national regulations related to CCUS technology and their national implementations are overviewed for five countries (Italy, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania and Russia) involved in the planned CCUS scenarios of the CLEANKER project. Only Russia did not ratified yet Paris Climate Agreement and Latvia, Lithuania and Russia are not yet parties of the London Protocol.
- National GHG and CO₂ fossil emissions are compared with the base 1990 year and their climate and energy strategic targets are discussed. Russia is one of the largest emitters and Estonia has one of the highest CO₂ emissions per capita in the world.

- CO₂ emissions from the cement industry should be considered as at the second place after the energy sector and could be captured and stored within common CCUS scenarios.
- The climate strategic targets should be increased in all the studied countries to reach the Paris targets and CCUS technology should be included in the list of technological priorities together with renewables and energy storage in all countries and in the BSR.
- CO₂ use options in the studied countries include CO₂ use for EOR, GER, mineral carbonation using waste materials, should be used in synergy with CO₂ storage and should compose business cases in both Italian and Baltic Scenarios.
- Additional CCUS regulations and political incentives are needed in all the studied countries. Specific laws for CO₂ storage and monitoring of emissions at the storage sites should be developed in Latvia and Russia.
- National, industrial and EU support are needed to start the first full CCUS projects in Italy, Baltic States and Russia.
- Educational and increasing public awareness activities supported by academic and research institutions and media support to explain benefits of climate change mitigation are needed for both scenarios and in the all countries.

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